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Project Acronym: WYRED

Project title: netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Periodic Technical Report

Part B

Period covered by the report: from 01/05/2018 to 31/10/2019

Periodic report: 2nd

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

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1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

- *Explain the work carried out during the reporting period in line with the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement.*
- *Include an overview of the project results towards the objective of the action in line with the structure of the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement including summary of deliverables and milestones, and a summary of exploitable results and an explanation about how they can/will be exploited².
(No page limit per work package but report shall be concise and readable. Any duplication should be avoided).*

The WYRED project has achieved its aims for the reporting period in line with the DoA. All deliverables and milestones are complete for the second period and the project as a whole (see Part A section 2. Deliverables and section 3. Milestones).

As regards exploitable results these can be divided into two areas. The first of these is the WYRED approach to working with young people for their empowerment. This methodology and the platform that supports it, has proved very valuable and in many cases transformative, in the contexts addressed by the project. It is also sufficiently robust and flexible (after development and fine-tuning over the course of the project) to be transferable to other contexts, and domains such as young people's well-being, environmental concerns, public health or other fields. The potential of this is being explored in the development of the WYRED Association. The other key exploitable results are the outputs of the research cycles (particularly in Year 3) and the insights derived from them, and from the dialogues and Delphi work. This set of results will be directly exploited through the WYRED Association by sharing them with other young people, policy makers and the wider society, particularly through our yearly WYRED Insights reports and related media, in order to ensure that all have the opportunity to develop a better understanding of young people's digital lives and ways of improving them as well.

1.1 Objectives

List the specific objectives for the project as described in section 1.1 of the DoA and described the work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of each listed objective. Provide clear and measurable details.

The main aim of the project is to give young people a voice, and a space to explore their concerns and interests in relation to digital society and share their perspectives and insights to stakeholders with other strata of society.

The objectives of the project have been achieved. Young people across more than seven countries have participated in three WYRED cycles during the project, and a wide range of international online conversations have taken place around concerns relating to the digital society (such as online safety, online information, gender, self- image, living on social media,

² Beneficiaries that have received Union funding, and that plan to exploit the results generated with such funding primarily in third countries not associated with Horizon 2020, should indicate how the Union funding will benefit Europe's overall competitiveness (reciprocity principle), as set out in the grant agreement.

and digital participation). Through this work the WYRED approach has been refined and streamlined and is now consolidated as an effective and enriching way of working with young people for their empowerment in the digital society. The WYRED Association has been set up to carry the work forward, both extending the approach to other contexts and adapting the methodology to other domains.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 1: WYRED PROCESSES DEFINITION

WP1 began on November 2016 (M1 of the Project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. WP1 Leader is BOUNDARIES. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.1.1 WP Highlights

The objective of WP1 was to provide a framework for the project and bring together all the different elements of the project. The bulk of the work in this WP took place at the start of the project. The process of discussion and definition of all the processes involved in WYRED in order to generate the first versions of the key WP deliverables - one the Process Handbook, and the other the Participant Protection Policy - had been instrumental in helping the partners to achieve an initial shared understanding of the WYRED approach as well as the decision-making and other processes involved in the functioning of the WYRED research cycle, the platform and the community.

Throughout the project the two deliverables played an important role as reference and orientation for the work. The Process Handbook is a set of guidelines and reflections on how WYRED works, and how it can be implemented in different contexts. The Participant Protection Policy focuses on the ethical dimension of the project. During the second period of the project, each of these documents has undergone a continuous process of updating and revision as the consortium has learned from the experience of the WYRED cycles. In the second period, this Work package worked closely with WP10, in the Working Group (1) that focused on the scope of WYRED.

The two Independent Ethical Reviews during the project were very positive about the original ethical positions as described in the Participant Protection Policy. In addition to this no ethical issues or incidents arose that would have led to a need to make substantial changes. In the case of the Process Handbook there was more work to do, as the WYRED cycle has been progressively refined and simplified, and the Handbook has been continuously updated to reflect this. The learning process, and the accompanying streamlining of the cycle has given the WYRED approach greater accessibility, flexibility and adaptability to different contexts, which we believe will be important in the post-funding phase, contributing to greater sustainability.

1.2.1.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

All partners were involved in the processes of reflection throughout the project that led to changes being made to the WYRED processes. The work was coordinated by BOUNDARIES, and this involved periodic specific conversations online and in project meetings to explore the changes that were required, which were then captured in the new versions of the WP deliverables.

1.2.1.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

The work was implemented appropriately and in timely manner so that it served its purpose as guidance and a reference point.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 1.3: Handbook creation (later versions).

Task 1.4 Participant Protection Policy (later versions).

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

D1.2 Processes Handbook v2

D1.3 Processes Handbook v3

D1.6 Participant Protection Policy v3.

D1.7 Participant Protection Policy v4.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the versions of the Processes Handbook, MS1, MS2 and MS3 have been achieved with the delivery of the versions of the handbook.

1.2.1.4. Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

The aim of the work done in WP1 was dual. On the one hand it was expected to anchor the project by providing a reference point and structuring the work, especially the research cycle, on the other it provided a process for capturing and comprehending the lessons we learned as we implemented the WYRED cycles through the project. It fulfilled both these functions and played a valuable role in drawing together and synthesising the work into a flexible accessible approach which was a central output of the WYRED project. It has helped partners with very different backgrounds and organisational cultures to reach a shared perspective. Increasingly also, as the project progressed the outputs of WP1 began to acquire value as central pillars in our sustainability strategies.

WYRED constitutes a new approach to work with young people, which is captured and set out in the two deliverables of this work package. They can be understood as reference guides to WYRED and as such they are the foundation for the future work that the WYRED Association will be carrying out. They are already proving useful as the basis for conversations with diverse bodies on potential adoption and adaptation to their contexts. One example is the UK NHS where the Handbook, and the approach it sets out is being discussed as a potential template for new approaches to policy research.

1.2.2 Work package 2: INCLUSION

WP2 began on November 2016 (M1 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. WP2 Leader is MOVES. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.2.1 WP Highlights

Inclusion in the WYRED project has been committed to an understanding of diversity that regards differences as normal and values the idea of anyone equally participating in all aspects of life and decision-making. Differences between individuals are regarded as an enrichment and as being normal. Inclusion values equality and equal participation of every member of society in all aspects of life, including civic, social, economic, and political activities, as well as in decision-making processes.

The main highlights of the last 18 months have been:

- Based on our common understanding of inclusion and diversity within the project, the partners were continuously informed about the status quo of inclusion in WYRED as given on the platform. This was done through the third inclusion report (D2.3) in October 2018 and in the run of the project meetings during the period.
- One further adaptation of the questionnaire to partners' needs was made in summer 2018 and led to the 4th parallel version of the questionnaire (3rd gender, religion, sexual orientation and ethnicity questions not displayed) used by Doga.
- The return rate of the questionnaire was consistently over 50 %, on October 31st, 2019 it was 54,45 %, which can be regarded as a satisfactory return rate, especially in regard to the fact that completion on the platform was not compulsory.
- The final Inclusion Report (D2.4) not only includes the data available on the platform, but also data from the partners and the facilitators working with the young people face to face who did not register for diverse reasons. In this way we got diversity data from a total of 1,670 young people. As regards expected impacts as set out in the DoA all targets were achieved.

1.2.2.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

MOVES is the lead partner for Work package 2. All partners were involved in WP2 and brought in their national experiences, which means that one person per partner took over the role of being a member of the WYRED inclusion team.

1.2.2.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

All tasks within WP 2 in the reporting time period were completed, which is essentially D2.3 delivered in time, whereas D2.4 was delayed for about one month (12/03/2019), as data was not yet available for analysis.

Tasks

The following task was implemented during this reporting period:

Task 3.3: Annual reports.

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

D2.3. Inclusion report 2.

D2.4. Inclusion report 3.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the production of the yearly Inclusion Reports. MS4, MS5 and MS6 have been achieved with the delivery of the relevant inclusion reports.

1.2.2.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

The processes in WP2 turned out to be a self-running process and as the evaluators suggested in their mid-term report, WP2 stepped back a bit with its activities in order not to hamper other processes in the cycles.

The inclusion questionnaire for WYRED is a living document. We are still planning a new adaptation for the post funding period which was found to be necessary when analysing data for D.2.4 (ethnicity question).

Though frequently used international diversity criteria were proposed and applied, the development of the questionnaire – mainly its operationalization - provoked numerous discussions and brought also many further ideas and inputs. Valuable cultural differences were surfaced, which finally resulted in four alternative/flexible ways of implementing the form.

In this way the questionnaire is well tested and gives a reliable impression of the participants' diversity. This means that we will go on using it in the WYRED Association especially as the data collected helps us to demonstrate the diversity of WYRED, which contributes to its sustainability.

1.2.3 Work package 3: WYRED PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT

WP3 began on January 2017 (M3 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. The technical team worked on the software development. WP3 Leader is USAL. All partners contributed to the definition of the platform requirements.

1.2.3.1 WP Highlights

The main aim of the WP3 was the definition and development of the WYRED Platform to provide the tools needed to support the different processes defined in the research framework, while facilitating the management of the knowledge generated by children and young people during the different activities conducted during the project.

The purpose of the platform was not to replace the social spaces where children and young people interact, but to provide a private, safe space for the participation of both young people and children. The use of social spaces where young people are already users had to be ruled out since none of the platforms where young people interact allow access to children under 14. Furthermore, existing social networks, despite attempts to comply with the GDPR, do not ensure the privacy of the personal data and information published in such spaces. The creation of a social network similar to Twitter, Instagram or Facebook was not the objective, since trends in the use of social networks not only depend on careful design, powerful functionality and a correct user experience, but there are many factors that influence the success of a social network, in fact, many social networks fail, such as Google Plus, Tuenti or Orkut.

The WYRED Platform is not a monolithic software platform. It consists of a set of Open Source tools and the people involved in the project - partners, stakeholders and young people between 7 and 30 years old. The WYRED Platform is a technological ecosystem (García-Peñalvo, 2016a), “a set of people and software components that are related to each other through information flows in a physical environment that provides the support for these flows” (García-Holgado, 2018). The main characteristics of this technological approach are the ability to evolve

in different ways and a strong set of human factors - users, methodology, management guidelines – that are treated with the same degree of importance as the software.

The WYRED Platform was designed from the start to be able to evolve throughout the project to adapt to the changing needs and problems encountered during the implementation of the WYRED cycle. The platform has been a living evolving component throughout the project, adapting to the needs of its users and supporting all activities and processes associated with the WYRED cycle. The aim is to continue with the evolution of the WYRED Platform after the end of the funding period in order to support WYRED Association activities.

It is important to note that technological design is not sufficient to ensure the participation of young people in the WYRED platform. It has been necessary to combine technology with education, and the management of expectations of children and young people regarding the nature of social media and software platforms. In general, the most effective uses have involved facilitated rather than stand-alone use. For this reason, facilitators as well as users are an intrinsic element of the WYRED Platform, with equal importance to software, and this is an element that will form an important part of the work on the platform in the post-funding period.

The platform is organized in multicultural interdisciplinary communities where young people share their ideas, and concerns about the digital society and their research projects with the support of facilitators from different European institutions and associations. The communities have different tools: forums to support conversations and coordinate research projects; a calendar to share dates and organize events or activities associated to the topic of the community; and a form to give visibility to the research projects. One of its main innovations, but also a challenge, is the strong commitment to user privacy and security; it is designed as a safe space in which children and young people can express themselves freely. Users need an invitation to register within the Platform and children under 14 years old (18 in AT) need parental consent in order to have access after finishing the registration. Besides this, privacy policies are in place to ensure the anonymity of young people, while allowing demographic information to be collected and stored in a separate tool.

Among the activities associated with WP3, beyond the development of the platform itself and the ecosystem approach, it is important to highlight the usability studies that were carried out in order to obtain reliable data to improve the platform. In particular, two usability studies were carried out. The first usability study with young people because was the basis for the following ones. It was conducted with students of the Degree in Social Education (University of Salamanca, Spain). 96 students worked with the WYRED Platform for 17 days (4-21 December 2017) with different roles, facilitator and participant, in different communities. The System Usability Scale (SUS) (Brooke, 1996) was used to measure the usability; it provides an effective, valid and reliable way to score the usability of a system (Brooke, 2013; Tullis & Stetson, 2004). Also, an open question was included in order to collect the main perceptions of the students regarding their experiences. This question provided feedback about the general thoughts about the platform, being the majority of them positive, although also some problems were detected that were solved in the months after the usability study. The usability study and its results were presented in the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) with an audience of about 2000 researchers, academics, and professionals (HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA) (García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018).

The second usability study was conducted targeting facilitators to reach insights about how these users value the WYRED Platform usability. This usability study was organized in two phases, a heuristic evaluation by four experts, two women and two men between 25 to 39 years old, and a usability questionnaire to collect experience of the facilitators of the WYRED Platform. The first phase was based on the heuristics proposed by Nielsen (1994), each expert navigated through the application several times observing all the screens and detecting the usability problems. The number of problems identified by each expert was small but the combination of all of them provided an input to improve the WYRED Platform and provide a stable final version. Regarding the second phase, 28 facilitators answered the Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) (version 3) (Sauro & Lewis, 2012). The responses were mostly positive and connected with the results of the heuristic evaluation. The study was presented in the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction 2019 (Orlando, Florida, USA) (García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & García-Holgado, 2019).

Finally, it is important to highlight that the WYRED Platform has been tested in a fully different context than the European one, namely with Brazilian university students. In particular, the instrument of the second Delphi has been used to identify the topics that interest young people in Brazil (88 answers) and to set up a set of social dialogues with a face-to-face and an online phase supported by the WYRED Platform. In this way, both the methodology and the platform have been tested beyond the controlled environment of the WYRED project. The successful outcome of this transfer has been accepted for presentation at WorldCist'20 - 8th World Conference on Information Systems and Technologies, to be held in Budva, Montenegro, 7 - 10 April 2020 (Knihs & García-Holgado, 2020).

1.2.3.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

Partners were involved in the definition of the WYRED Platform from the beginning of the project. Their ideas and requirements were collected as a starting point to provide the first definition of the platform. They were the first testing users of the alpha version of the platform during summer 2017. After that, they provided continuous feedback to solve problems, improve the functionality, or include new functionality to support processes associated with other WPs such as WP2 or WP7. Moreover, since the platform was designed as a technological ecosystem, all partners had an important role as the facilitators in charge of the actual usage of the platform. All partners collaborated to distribute the questionnaire of the second usability study among their facilitators.

The technical team from USAL was in charge of the software definition and development following the requirements provided by the partners and taking into account the legal issues associated with children and young people, as well as the data protection law. They provided different ways to achieve the objectives proposed by all partners and carry out the implementation of the different versions until the current version was reached. Also, the technical team conducted the usability studies described above. Furthermore, a communication channel with all partners was maintained to inform them about the improvements in the platform and receive continuous feedback from them.

1.2.3.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Several activities and outcomes were carried out. In particular, seven versions (three major and four minor) were launched with different functionalities and improvements. It is important to note that several of the versions are associated with the results obtained in the usability studies, with the current version being the result of solving the most important problems detected during the second usability study. Also, the tasks planned in the last report were completed. The

deliverable D3.4_v1.3 describes in detail the activities and outcomes. Here we highlight the main ones:

- Redesign of the communities in order to solve some problems detected during the usability studies.
- The email of the users of the platform is private to ensure anonymity. For this reason, it is not possible to send direct messages. To send a direct message to the users we developed the “mass message”, a functionality managed by the admin and the facilitators in order to notify something really important to the children, young people and stakeholders in the platform.
- Fully responsive design.
- A warning was added to the public communities not recommended for children under 14 years old.
- Research projects have a space to comment, so users can give feedback about the project directly in the specific project space instead of the general community space in which the project is located.
- A new version of the form to publish research projects in order to support translation of the main information into another language was developed. For example, for a project in Spanish it is possible to provide a title and a short description of the project also in English, so all participants in the Platform can have an idea of the project objective.
- A management interface to organize the forums into different categories inside a community.

The impact indicator related to WP3 was achieved through the two usability studies carried out. A total of 98 testers with different profiles and nationalities were involved in the usability studies.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 3.1: Definition of platform requirements (for the later versions).

Task 3.2: Platform development (later versions).

Task 3.3: Initial usability testing (we have continued with the usability testing of the later versions).

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

D3.3. Platform v2.

D3.4. Platform v3.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the release of three version of the platform. MS7 Platform v1, MS8 Platform v2 and MS9 Platform v3 have been successfully achieved. The first major version of the Platform was launched on M7, the second major version on M19, and the third major version on M34. In the meantime, several minor versions were launched. The deliverables for this period D3.3 and D3.4 were delivered on time.

1.2.3.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

Users' needs change over time. For this reason, the WYRED Platform is framed as a technological solution in constant evolution. Although the methodological framework was defined from the beginning of the project, the platform needed to be adapted to new methodological decisions and support new workflows that may emerge. In order to achieve this

challenge, we had to conceive the platform as a technological ecosystem, and we had to improve the communication channels with all partners. We have had more bilateral online meetings with leads of other WPs in order to cover all their technical needs through the platform. The key lesson learned is that in this context, design and user education have to run hand in hand and facilitated use in a private safe space such as this is more effective than standalone use.

The multilingual aspect was also a challenge. Connecting the platform with an automatic translation service was ruled out from the beginning because of the high costs. The free services such as Google Translate do not work well. The platform is multilingual because the interface is available in the different languages involved in the project, but the content created by the users is only in the language in which they shared. In this sense, the platform is multilingual, with communities in different languages, but the content of that communities is not translated.

The WYRED Platform is the key exploitable result of this work package. It provides a useful space to support co-creation processes, to develop research projects, to support international discussions about different topics, and to connect people across the world with similar ideas and objectives. These results based on the activities conducted within the project are now being complemented by the case study mentioned in Brazil with young people located in different spaces, working on different digital society topics through a set of communities in the WYRED Platform, with the support of a facilitator trained in the WYRED methodology but who was not involved in the project.

1.2.4 Work package 4: BUILDING THE WYRED NETWORK

WP4 began on December 2016 (M2 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. WP4 Leader is YEU. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.4.1 WP Highlights

The aim of the WP was to help the consortium build and maintain a sustainable WYRED Network. It assists outcomes of other WPs to be more impactful and achieve meaningful engagement and connection of young people with stakeholders and decision makers. The consortium, since the beginning of the process, highlighted its importance in order to reach out to a critical mass of both participants and stakeholders. Through a set of preliminary activities and understanding that this is an ongoing process, the WYRED Network has slowly grown and become stronger throughout the project.

Building up the WYRED Network, required a lot of coordination and contribution by all partners. The network developed steadily, during the first 18th months, growing continuously and becoming stronger. Building on processes like the initial stakeholders contact, the Delphi survey and most important the outcomes of WP6 and WP7, we engaged young people, stakeholders and decision makers, using elements including the consortium manifesto and an initial children and young people's manifesto which brought together the objectives and intentions of the project and the WYRED process. Using these tools, it was easier to empower partners in reaching out to stakeholders and initiating a dialogue with participants around their concerns in relation to the digital society, and they have continued to be useful throughout the project. There were also questionnaires, the creation of the project visual identity, participants training activities, coordination, implementation and participation in the events which gave us opportunities to present the WYRED approach and engage more stakeholders thus enriching the network.

The WYRED network continued to grow in the second 18 months by strengthening the existing network through more engagement at all levels of partners' work – local, regional/national and European, building new connections and creating synergies with similar initiatives or promoting WYRED methodology as the complementary to the one already in use by WYRED stakeholders. In practice, that meant using the WYRED methodology in addition to the ones already typically used – for example, in non-formal education, a lot of attention is given to learning by doing and research accompanied by social dialogues were new aspects for many youth associations. Although there was some initial scepticism, the approach was further used by WYRED staff in their own local initiatives or as preparatory phases in other projects including both local and international levels.

This proved to be a good formula for success as more young people and other stakeholders became interested in joining the discussions and making their contributions. In the second part of the process it was easier for partners to build connections and involve young people and other stakeholders due to the fact that, by word of mouth, WYRED became known among the communities of practitioners and those in direct contact with young people.

For young people it is not so common that they are asked for their opinions, or to give feedback because they don't have a lot of trust in institutions – one of the messages that emerged through the creation of the new version of the Manifesto in the second period was “don't listen to us only when you need us”. Taking that on board, there was an adjustment to the networking strategy to make sure all networking focused on this rather than simply talking about WYRED and in this way the approach to young people in networking actions was participatory and with full autonomy for them to express their opinions, explore the topics and recommend actions.

The highlights of the second 18 months period of WYRED in that sense are:

- We participated in the annual [European Youth Event](#) organized by European Parliament that brings together more than 8000 young people to Strasbourg with young representatives of YEU, MOVES, USAL and DOGA. In 2018 this was also an opportunity for [WYRED participants](#) to take part in the debate organized by some of the partners on the topic “Growing up in a digital society: What matters most to young people?”- Event at the European Parliament (with the participation of MEPs – Ms Terry Reintke and Mr Brando Benifei, YFJ – Ms Mari Strømsvåg, YEU – Matej Manevski)” and “The digital revolution continues: what will be the next steps?” - Workshop at Yo!Fest Village - this event started new cooperation with some of the MEPs that later on supported WYRED approach and its promotion by taking part in direct discussions with young people via WYRED platform and social media especially in the WYRED Online Festival.
- [University on Youth and Development](#) (UYD) organized by North South Centre of Council of Europe every September in the south of Spain gathering around 250 young people was the place where the WYRED approach together with platform were presented in both 2018 and 2019 by representatives of YEU, USAL and Oxfam and where youth organisations and young people had the opportunity to contribute to the revision of the Manifesto (in 2018 edition), get information about international conversations, methodology and topics (both 2018 and 2019), and join the WYRED Association (2019).
- A revised version of the Manifesto was created in the period of June-November 2018 as a result of the consultative process among young people around Europe. More than 300 young people, through online and face to face consultations in different occasions

and events, took part directly in the Manifesto revision as the WYRED partners believe that Manifesto should be an open and “living” document and a collection of young people’s thoughts and recommendations towards the policy makers. Based on the input of young people, WYRED partners created short and long versions.

- [YO!Fest 2019](#) organised by the European Youth Forum during the European Youth Week 2019 in Brussels was the place where some of the WYRED facilitators of online conversations [presented the WYRED approach](#) and work done to the present stakeholders expanding further the network of WYRED and its impact on young people and organisations working directly with them. The discussion took place as part of the “Memes Dreams and Activism: being a human rights activist in the era of algorithm” part of the programme.
- Involving relevant stakeholders in WYRED conversations was an effort that took place throughout the WYRED cycle in spaces such as [European Youth Forum](#) or the [Youth Intergroup](#) with MEPs in the European Parliament and Lifelong Learning Platform during [LLL Week 2018](#) and the working group on Digital Learning.

1.2.4.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

In order to develop a sustainable WYRED Network, it was necessary to support and follow up the work and outcomes of all WPs, while including all partners in the process. As expected by WP4 description, all partners had to and were engaged in most of the deliverables of the package.

The first process and initial example was the engagement in the review of Manifestos and further on their dissemination. As the youth manifesto was the initial version, it was expected that partners use it to work with young people and children to pass on that outcome and build with them the feeling of ownership.

In the second 18 months, the WYRED network continued growing at different levels of partners’ work – local, national/regional and European. Each partner was making significant efforts to promote the WYRED approach among different stakeholders, with two different focuses:

1. Their own existing network.
2. New stakeholders identified based on the scope of work and potential synergies.

All the partners further engaged young people from their own networks and in response to comments made by the reviewers created synergies with other stakeholders working directly with young people which led to more structured participation in international conversations on six topics the consortium had identified through the Cycle 1 dialogues and Delphi processes:

1. Internet Safety.
2. Information.
3. Gender.
4. Self-Image.
5. Digital Participation
6. Living on Social Media.

Based on the interest of their own networks, partners took the lead on specific topics in international conversations together with online facilitation and gatekeepers.

In this period, since the WYRED approach was already consolidated, network building gained different dynamics and became increasingly complementary with WP8 (Valorisation) working

together within the Working Group focused on WYRED and society by identifying and reaching out to new stakeholders, continuously spreading the word about WYRED, disseminating the achievements through participating in or organising events on WYRED related topics.

Besides, all partners made additional efforts in the period of June-November 2018 to revise Manifesto by opening consultations for young people in their networks with YEU and Oxfam taking a lead in the collection of recommendations and final revision of the document that led to creation of full and short version. The process of the Manifesto was very important for the WP4 development as it gathered young people as individuals and on behalf of different youth organisations working at European level (IUSY, JEF, AEGEE, OBESSU, EEE-YFU, EFIL, DYPALL, Erasmus Student Network) and numerous organisations working at local level such as MOJU - Association – Movimento Juvenil em Olhão, USB - United Societies of Balkans, TOG - Toplum Gönüllüleri Vakfı, CID - Centre for Intercultural Dialogue, RCLC - Resource Centre Leskovac, CIM Horizonty – Centrum Inicjatyw Młodzieżowych HORYZONTY, IUS - Institute for Ukrainian Studies, FRI - Foundation of Regional Initiatives) moving WYRED beyond the partners' usual beneficiaries and collecting relevant information and input from young people using participatory approach and allowing them to be fully autonomous.

Local networks

Apart from work at European level with an aim to promote the top to bottom approach (by reaching out to platforms and networks that spread information about WYRED further to their members at local level), each partner focused on creating their own WYRED environments. In Northern Ireland, Early Years and PYE have worked directly with the Northern Ireland Commissioner for Children and Young People (NICCY) which results in the Commissioner's participation in WYRED Online Festival, Day 1. Additionally, Early Years has also developed cooperation with Children's Research Network, International Network on Peacebuilding and European Network of Ombudspersons for Children, Dublin Youth Centre and had opportunity to present the WYRED approach and results.

MOVES in Austria has showcased WYRED to Center for Inclusive Schools Vienna 1170 and Ministry for Research and Education while several other organisations such as , Sprungbrett, efeu, Mädchencafé, FIT, Poika, Hertha Fiirnberg Schools, BG BRG Klosterneuburg and Teachers College Vienna got acquainted with the WYRED process especially in the context of the Online Festival.

Boundaries in the UK focused on building the network by presenting the WYRED approach to staff and students at a large number of schools (among them the MUN network, Ralph Allen school, Hayesfield School, Haberdashers Aske), local MPs at Brit School in Croydon, ex Shadow Schools Minister at Houses of Parliament, to education staff (Education and wellbeing event EDEN) and Public Health Policy research group experts.

In Israel, TAU reached out to numerous stakeholders through “Tel Aviv Summer Youth University” and by presenting WYRED approach to local high schools (TAU School of Education)

DOGA Schools have focused on working with schools and universities (Gaziantep Doğa Schools, Ankara Eryaman Doga Schools, Bursa Özlüce Doga Schools, Ataşehir 1 Doğa

Schools, Sehir and Istinye University, The Libertarian Youth Summer Camp, Acarkent Doga Junior High Schools, Acarkent High Schools and Çamlıca Anatolian Religious High School for girls) in all parts of Turkey to involve young people of various age groups to have their say in the WYRED project. The network has been built with sports trainers, teachers, head of teachers, lawyers, parents and decision-makers to use the WYRED approach when working with young people.

Oxfam has partnered up with media outlets and universities in Italy to promote the WYRED approach while YEU in Belgium has reached out to local youth centres, organisations and local antennas of student movements to showcase how WYRED can be a complementary methodology to the ones already typically used in youth work (JES and Foyer - youth centres in Molenbeek, Dynamo in Uccle, JOETZ – Flemish organization working with young people, student associations in VUB, ULB and St Louis University and local scout groups). YEU worked additionally on promoting the WYRED as a channel of communication between policy makers and young people and with this approach managed to reach out to several members of the European Parliament.

USAL has further built cooperation with different universities in which they have showcased WYRED - Universidad Nacional de San Agustín de Arequipa (Arequipa, Peru), Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie (Sao Paulo, Brazil), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), University of León (Spain)

Each of the stakeholders approached, interaction created and word spread about WYRED meant further building the WYRED network that later on met either through conversations in the platform or during the WYRED Online Festival.

WYRED Network has been built using the horizontal and decentralized rather than vertical approach as each of the partners mapped their stakeholders based on their local contexts and realities. This enriched the network as the consortium reached out to stakeholders active in variety of social contexts – education (schools, universities), policy makers (local and European MPs, institutions, ombudspersons and governments), youth organisations active in non-formal education, media, researchers and experts.

All the networking efforts led to higher interest in Association and its membership that are explained in more details in WP8.

1.2.4.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Focusing on creating, building and sustaining a network, required proper coordination, learning throughout the process, continued evaluation and adaptation to needs and circumstances, led by YEU and supported by all partners.

With coordination and focus on each task, the consortium aimed to achieve the maximum possible quality of each outcome deriving from each task. Linking the implementation of the tasks with the impact or product of other WPs and processes, there were delays concerning the finalization of these outcomes (presented in the “Highlights”). Throughout the process, the outreach and the link to policy depended on tangible outcomes produced by other WPs or tasks under the coordination of other partners. Through the initial production of necessary outcomes,

YEU and partners, were able to reach out to more young people, stakeholders and to some decision makers. An example was MOVES (Austrian Partners) sharing position papers to local stakeholders. In other cases, YEU took the opportunity, using its' experience and location, to reach out to vital stakeholders and decision makers both at local and European level. Some examples were members and structures of [Lifelong Learning Platform \(All Digital\)](#) [European Youth Forum \(AEGEE, Scouts\)](#), attending EU Institutions or CoE events and using these occasions to share information, bring on board and showcase outcomes of the project (e.g. EQF 10th Anniversary - Reaching out National Agencies, Education Entities etc.).

After the initial period and achieving full understanding of what kind of approach the partners could adopt regarding the network building considering their own realities and contexts, the second 18 months of network building was smoother as partners had more tangible results and outcomes to work with when reaching out to stakeholders at different levels.

As the WP lead, YEU was able to present the WYRED approach in a different manner to relevant stakeholders working directly with young people as a new methodology that allows full autonomy to young people and promotes active participation and critical thinking empowerment. Different partners had different challenges in the process of network building depending on the already existing practices in their own work. The specifics of WYRED approach from one side is full youth autonomy which is an essential principle in the youth sector but not in others and participatory research from another side that is not so common among youth organisations and there was a need among partners to balance these two sides and find the most appropriate way to engage young people.

In this period, YEU continued to provide input to the youth related policies at the level of European Union and Council of Europe giving recommendations based on the WYRED approach and reaching out to young people directly creating a WYRED critical mass. The outreach towards policy makers and young people was done at different levels – through consultations on Erasmus plus programme implementation, EU Youth Dialogue participation and youth conferences organized by EU presidency cycles – Austria and Bulgaria in 2018 and Romania and Finland in 2019 and through regular input at the level of Council of Europe through its co-management system – Advisory Council on Youth and finding synergies with, particularly, No Hate Speech Movement (NHSM) working on similar issues as WYRED – internet safety, cyberbullying and gender.

All partners actively involved young people in events where they had direct contacts with policy makers, among others European Youth Event in May 2018, University on Youth and Development 2018 and 2019, YO!Fest 2019. Specific efforts were additionally made to reach out to younger MEPs (below 35) and ensure direct contact with young people with an idea to demystify the policy development and decision making process and encourage young people to actively question and give contribution to society development with specific emphasis on digital society and its regulation.

All the impact targets for the second period were achieved, and the main outcomes of the WYRED networking activity at the end of the project are several circles of stakeholders at different levels that go beyond project partnership and include the whole of Europe – with certain overlapping moments mainly regarding approach to young people and ensuring that they have full trust in the process with their voices heard by policy makers and clearly planned follow up actions focused on following approaches:

- Amplifying youth voices.

- Strengthening youth views through youth-led research.
- Connecting youth with decision-makers.
- Broadening understanding of the digital society.
- Making youth perspectives matter.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 4.1: Development of network manifesto (later versions).

Task 4.5: Policy/youth outreach (continuous during the project).

Task 4.6: Participant training (continuous during the project).

Deliverables

The following deliverable was produced in this reporting period:

D4.4. Initial networking report 2 M24

Milestones

All WYRED tasks in the second reporting period were on time and all the challenges were positively resolved by adapting the WYRED approach to the contexts of the partners while keeping the participatory principles in involving stakeholders, specifically young people. D4.4 was delivered on time, while tasks 4.5 and 4.6 remained as ongoing throughout the WYRED implementation.

1.2.4.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

In the second half of the project, based on lessons learned previously, some adjustments were made. Some processes such as the Stakeholder Questionnaire, once there were results to discuss were no longer necessary and were phased out. Work was also done to focus on the potentials and strengths of each partner in a more targeted and productive way to ensure the sustainability of the network. It was also possible to make much more extensive use of the outputs of the cycles with tangible outcomes of WP5, WP6 and WP7 which became the basis for the network growth, which it should be said was increasingly part of the same overall thrust as the valorisation activity, and the new working group structure facilitated this well.

These adjustments helped to ensure smooth network building from 18th month onwards. By finetuning and streamlining the narrative for WYRED and adjusting the approach to stakeholders while absolutely keeping the youth autonomy as a main principle, the WYRED network kept growing at different levels – local, regional/national and European.

The main lessons learned to be taken into the WYRED Association activity going forward can be summarized as following:

- It is important not to forget that young people and children are a very diverse and heterogenous group of different backgrounds (religion, culture, orientation), age (cultural background affects defining the age of the young – both in lower and higher age limit), educational and social status or even political affiliation. WYRED cannot represent whole generations or take into consideration only the needs or practices of one while risking neglecting the other. Instead, WYRED stayed open for all the opinions and thoughts of young people from various backgrounds even if that required additional efforts from all the partners.
- The terminology of the WYRED project had to be adjusted to young people and this should always be kept in mind – complex terms and phrases can be more intimidating than appealing if we are aiming at approaching young people and children with fewer opportunities.
- Young people should be encouraged to participate and kept being reminded that their voice matters even if they use simpler phrases or their needs seem to be simple and not “life changing”. The WYRED Consortium was using different ways to interact with young people and children and aimed at providing them opportunity to express their thoughts through audio, video and any other kind of materials.
- Young people and children need to be constantly informed about the opportunities: using the platform or creating opportunities to interact with decision and policy makers.
- The WYRED approach is about young people and children and needs to be constantly adapted to their needs and aspirations, instead of expecting them to adapt to already existing approaches.
- The WYRED approach can be complementary to already existing methodologies and this is how it can ensure its sustainability. Diverse conversations are under way in this regard, especially in the youth work, non-formal education and formal education (schools and universities) contexts.

- Horizontal and decentralised approach to networking, tailored to local and specific contexts of each partner create significant and higher reach out to stakeholders that would otherwise be omitted in case of a uniformed one.

1.2.5 Work package 5: SOCIAL DIALOGUE PHASE

WP5 began on February 2017 (M4 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project (estimated end in DoA M25). WP5 Leader is EARLY YEARS. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.5.1 WP Highlights

The implementation of Social Dialogues with Children and Young People during the 2nd period involved dialogues in both the second and third cycles of WYRED as well as the online conversations cycle in the final year of the project.

The social dialogues functioned well, a wide diversity of participants engaged in the processes, and a valuable set of perspectives were shared. A substantial number of young people across seven European countries, and a wide range of ages and socio-economic backgrounds, have been given an opportunity to share their views and explore their diverse understandings of issues that concern them.

In all the dialogues, there was clear interest in the topics and interesting insights have arisen, especially in relation to the differences in priorities between young people and the stakeholders that work with them. They constituted a valuable opportunity to engage students in analysing, reflecting and critically thinking about their own generation in terms of what they identify as their principal concerns and problems.

KEY SUCCESS

From the perspective of participants (C&YP):

- The engagement of young people through the process, their emerging agency, and their sense of ownership of that process.
- In many cases there was also a reflection around their degree of engagement in society and decision-making.
- The result of the process was frequently that the young people involved left with a sense of empowerment through sharing their knowledge and perspectives, and furthermore that the issues that concerned them were also relevant for their peers and for society.
- For many the discussions also involved exploration of core values and views of the future.

From the perspective of the WYRED cycle implementation:

- Most importantly from the perspective of the WYRED cycle, the discussions provide the momentum and the ideas to move forward into the research phase.
- In this stage of the WYRED research cycle children and young people ENGAGE with each other in dialogues to define the exact questions that they would like to focus on.
- The dialogues engender lively and energetic debate among young people principally on themes related to the digital society though the approach may be used in other domains.

- Frequently, other issues and topics of interest were brought up by the C&YP themselves. A wide range of potential research areas were identified throughout this process and this will be explored further in the post-funding phase.
- The social dialogue phase has provided a unique opportunity for a range of stakeholders and most importantly our C&YP to be fully engaged in process that will put them at the heart of research involving the online world which is part of their everyday lives. It provides useful insights that have been harvested for the yearly WYRED Insights report.

1.2.5.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

All partners organised and facilitated a range of social dialogues to engender the research questions to inform the research projects. Templates which evolved as the project progressed were streamlined in the second period, and made available for partners to report on the activity. Reports were returned to WP Leader within agreed timeframes throughout the cycles.

1.2.5.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Throughout the second period through cycles 2 and 3 all partners organised and moderated in language of their own country a variety of social dialogues as part of the cycles, as well as organising and participating in the online conversations cycle. In all cycles the dialogues served their purpose of generating research questions and motivation to carry on through to the research stage of the cycle. All the impact targets for the second period were achieved.

Together with WP6 and WP7, this WP formed part of the WYRED as research Working Group (4) and the work done between these WPs was instrumental in streamlining the WYRED approach, and particularly bringing together reporting and evaluation processes into a simpler process.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

- Task 5.1: Preparation for dialogues (later cycles).
- Task 5.2: Synchronous dialogue sessions (later cycles).
- Task 5.3: Asynchronous dialogue sessions (later cycles).
- Task 5.4: Analysis (later cycles).
- Task 5.5: Key research questions (later cycles).

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

- D5.2. Corpus of session reports v2.
- D5.4. Key research questions v2.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP related to the collection of the Cycle Key research questions. MS11 and MS12 First and Second Cycle Key research questions were successfully achieved.

1.2.5.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research and exploitable results

A variety of lessons were learned through the WYRED Social Dialogues:

ENGAGEMENT - children and young people are to a large extent immersed in a set of activities that take up most of their time, and their free time is precious. Competition for attention with existing activities. So, it is advisable to complement existing activities where possible where

C&YP are already engaged (e.g. at school). It should not seem like work but a fun and interesting project to be involved in.

PARTICIPATION - sustained engagement is much harder to commit to than participation in a single event, such as a youth panel.

DIVERSITY – WYRED is committed to diversity and inclusion, however the easiest children and young people to access are to be found in middle-class schools with receptive families, the challenge is to move beyond this context. Though this has been achieved to some extent, more active policies are to be pursued in the WYRED Association.

Within the second period, on the recommendation of the evaluators, the focus in the social dialogues was narrowed to the six themes around the digital lives of the young participants (see WP4)

The Social Dialogues were organised and facilitated based on the recommendations of the previous cycles. Children and young people were brought together in schools, colleges, youth centres and facilities in over 20 countries across the three WYRED cycles of activity. Facilitators, teachers and youth workers used the social dialogue phase of the process to explain and outline the thematic structures of the project, encouraging the participants to develop research interests and questions within these parameters, ensuring that it was their own particular interests that would come to drive their further engagement. With the next steps, the children and young people were now motivated and inspired to take active control over the process. Their facilitators became back seat passengers in this moving vehicle. Through this process of taking charge of their learning and shaping the questions that they wanted to research, the children and young people became their own agents of change.

It is clear that from the experience of being active participants within this research process that the children and young people were allowed to develop their own voice, ask their own questions and formulate their own responses. They progressed an agenda that was set by them.

Cycle 1: 32 Social dialogue sessions with 550 Children and Young People.

Cycle 2: 76 Social dialogue sessions with 538 Children and Young People.

Cycle 3: 50 Social dialogue sessions with 657 Children and Young People.

Of the 50 social dialogues held in Cycle 3, almost 70% were held with the same groups of children and young people. The remaining 30% tended to be organised as one-off events, usually as a full day workshop. The more typical approach was to work with a group of children and young people over a number of sessions, whereby the WYRED themes could be presented and discussed in some detail, before moving onto the research phases. On average some 13 children and young people participated in each social dialogue. The highest proportion of these participants were aged between 14 and 19 years (45%), with the older cohort of participants aged over 20 making up 38% and the youngest group aged 9 to 13 years at 17%.

Through the social dialogue workshops and sessions, the most common WYRED themes addressed were associated with “Living on social media, living with stress” and “Access to reliable information, and fake news, media literacy”.

The approach taken by facilitators varied depending on the age profile of the participants and the settings. For example, in working with young people in youth centres, one partner described the process:

“In all the sessions we are using non-formal education as a tool to ensure that young people express themselves freely and if they wish to do so. The techniques we are usually using are brainstorming, role-plays, and discussions. In the social dialogues we would start with brainstorming to see what will be the first thoughts of young people that come to their minds when it comes to the topics. Then we would group the comments into more specific topics that seemed similar and split into small groups. In smaller groups, there was one participant in charge of taking care of time and keeping notes as well as ensuring that the discussion doesn't go into a completely different topic. We were aiming at gathering information and creating draft research questions that young people will further explore in small groups, online or offline.”

Through Cycle 3, opportunities for greater online engagement were promoted and taken up by children and young people from across the partner countries and centre. Through a series of structured online conversations, built over a fortnight at a time, classrooms came together synchronously across Europe to share their work and their conclusions. These were videoed and shared for further discussion. Students and academics made use of these fortnights to examine research approaches and tools, often through asynchronous discussion threads. Ongoing conversations continue to be facilitated through the platform. The success of these engagements is linked to the fact that the children and young people are setting their agenda.

Two trends became visible during the final cycle as the body of WYRED work was increasing. Greater involvement in online activities: through Cycle 3, as a greater volume of research was being produced, the children and young people became keener to share their results and make use of the spaces being provided. As more opportunities were created for the sharing and using of different online spaces (Online Conversation Fortnights, Online Festival, etc.) children and young people became more active users.

Partners were asked, in relation to Cycle 3, what the most relevant and significant insights coming out of the Social Dialogue session(s) relating to the WYRED themes were, and these have been incorporated into the Cycle 3 Insights report.

C&YP across all the partners, proved to have their fingers on the pulse of many of the topics discussed, with a wide variety of points of view in terms of assessing and solving the challenges faced. The common thread across all their participation was the eagerness and energy to contribute towards change.

The opportunity to engage with YP from other countries seemed appealing to them and was a good hook for them to stay involved through the next phases.

Young people want to make a difference but then they get easily disappointed with low response from their peers who are not interested be active citizens

An impressive 122 research questions were developed from the Social Dialogues in Cycle 3 – see Appendix 1 in the Second Cycle Evaluation Report Deliverable number WP7_D7.4.

1.2.6 Work package 6: PARTICIPANT RESEARCH PHASE

WP6 began on April 2017 (M6 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project (estimated end in DoA M32). WP6 Leader is DOGA. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.6.1 WP Highlights

This work package focused on the research phase of the WYRED cycle, where the consortium facilitated a wide range of research activities with groups of children and young people. The research activities were shaped by the Activity Toolkit. The WP leader collated information and instructions on research methodologies which would typically suit the topics emerging from the Delphi and from the Social Dialogues. Different and locally relevant strategies to involve children and young people in the WYRED project were used, underpinned by a broad selection of communication channels (e.g. word of mouth, email, social media, telephone, etc.) and events (e.g. workshops, seminars, etc.). Together with WP5 and WP7, this WP formed part of the WYRED as research Working Group (4) and the work done between these WPs was instrumental in streamlining the WYRED approach, and particularly bringing together reporting and evaluation processes into a simpler process.

Most research activities were initially carried out locally, but then exhibited internationally through the WYRED platform. This allowed participants to exchange opinions, insights, best known methods etc. with peers across the participating countries. In the initial phases this kind of exchange was mainly unilateral, i.e. students from one country commented on projects from another country because the platform is not an immediate medium of communication to young people, who are so accustomed to more widely used social media. This changed in the second period with the international online conversations where much more interaction took place around the projects and the issues they raised.

A variety of creative projects were carried out, including some more conventional research projects. All projects produced a variety of artefacts, deliverables such as reports, images, graphs, videos, prototypes, etc., created during the research process. The evidence of the artefacts produced by every project was uploaded onto the WYRED project platform by the project leaders. The outcomes of the research activities were consolidated and summarised and informed the evaluation activity covered by WP7. The outcome of the evaluation then enabled the managers of WP6 to make the necessary adjustments for the following cycle. This included the revision, adaptation and further development of the Activity Toolkit, which was a continuous process through the project. These processes were streamlined efficiently through the coordinated work of Working Group 4.

The WP6 deliverables which underwent a continuous process of update from cycle to cycle were:

- Activity toolkits (D6.1-D6.2); the generative research activities toolkit consists of templates and guidelines; it was created by the lead research partner in collaboration with some of the youth partners, and it is available on the WYRED platform for all participants.
- Activity artefacts collections (D6.3-D6.4); a wide variety of artefacts (e.g. videos, sculptures, publications, music, reports, images, etc.) were produced during the participant research phase in each cycle and stored on the WYRED Platform.

1.2.6.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

As part of the creation process for the activity toolkit, Doğa coordinated the input from all partners, and incorporated relevant feedback into the final version. Doğa also delivered instructions on how to use the toolkit and provided support as required. All partner organisations adopted the toolkit and oversaw its deployment through the local research projects and provided input for later versions.

Partner organisations oversaw projects which delivered artefacts, and collated relevant information for further analysis (i.e. participant type and numbers, etc.). Some of the projects were translated from the local language into English, to promote exchanges at international level. The exchanges were initiated and moderated by the project owners, central co-ordination was managed by Doğa and USAL. All the partner organisations facilitated the formation of research groups made up of participants previously engaged in the social dialogue phase (WP5). Some of the groups were pre-existing, as they were formed by participants coming from the same organisation, school or youth club. Other groups were created ad hoc around a specific research question. The partner organisations facilitated the exchanges within the group, as necessary, ensuring the group remained as autonomous as possible. Groups then implemented the activity they designed, following their own plans and expectations, and presented their ongoing work throughout the process in their project space on the WYRED platform.

The partners carried out projects focused mainly on the virtual world but with a wide range of perspectives, taking into consideration impacts and reverberations in the actual world, with in-depth analysis of trends, facts, risks, etc. Topics included the genesis and impact of fake news, the intended and the actual roles of social media and influencers, health risks associated with social media, cyberbullying, gender stereotyping, etc. It also analysed impact on specific target audiences, e.g. migrants or young digital citizens, as well as the role and impact of new technologies, such as Big Data and the Internet of Things. Overall, the corpus of findings provides an excellent overview of how C+YP experience and witness the interface between virtual and actual world.

Looking across the partnership, YEU facilitated a series of projects on the use of the digital world to improve democracy, education, employment opportunities and even urban planning. At Doğa there was interest among the participants in everyday aspects such as ‘nomophobia’ (the fear of mobile phones, as often displayed by teachers and parents alike), the correlation between spending time online and educational outcomes or even social relationships. Lots of attention was also given to the evolution of gender stereotypes fomented by the digital world, with a very specific focus on the changing ‘voice’ of female characters in literature and folk songs.

A specific topic which arose at TAU was the concept of ‘Digital Addiction’, its implications, ramifications and potential solutions. The research work supported by MOVES focused on criteria to choose a computer and on how to build a robot. Unsurprisingly, given the young age of its participants, Early Years in Northern Ireland facilitated tried and tested, pen and paper based offline approaches like mind-mapping, posters, etc. There were however online activities included, most notably Skype sessions with their peers from Doğa School in Istanbul, where they shared and debated points of view about social media aspects. All the activities were very appropriate for the age group and there was greater emphasis on behavioural aspects, such as trusting others and being polite online. The research done by groups coordinated by the University of Salamanca focused heavily on stereotypes, its formation and reinforcement through social media. A very specific angle was taken by a group who looked at the influence of internet on gender stereotyping in sports. The work supported by Boundaries covered aspects of self-image, as well as of aspects of negative representation of specific groups (e.g. LGBT+

community, younger vs older generations, ethnic minorities/colourism, etc.). A very peculiar and interesting focus was given by a project looking at the impact of banter and memes online.

1.2.6.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

In the second period the activity of this WP formed a smooth part of the WYRED cycle, in which the young participants carried out their research projects. While the first period work involved creation and definition, the second period focused more on refining and streamlining the process, working together with the other WPs in the Working Group.

Actual deliverables of WP6 in Cycle 1, 2 and 3

Quantitative Indicators	Target value	1st cycle value	2 nd & 3 rd cycle value	TOTAL
Average number of active participants per country per cycle	30	280	99+109=208	488
Average number of research activities per country per cycle	5	5	7+ 17=24	29
Average number of research activities types per cycle	5	5	12+19=31	36
Number of artefacts generated per cycle	80	104	52+ 134=186	290

As can be seen from the table above, the numbers of project delivered were consistently and significantly well above the targets set.

Artefacts were uploaded on the WYRED project platform by the respective project leads. The artefacts represent a wide variety of formats, and they reflect the creativity and the dedication of the participants. Participants from across partner organisations worked in groups to design and implement their own activities, with the inclusion of external participants. To this end, international discussion groups were formed on the WYRED platform. Groups were able to present their ongoing work as public projects in the common area on the WYRED platform, as well as in the respective community areas created for them by the partner organisations. The topics covered included influencers on social media, digital footprints, online safety, online self-image, gender stereotypes and equality on the internet, young people and adults on social media and digital participation.

Tasks

- The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:
 - Task 6.1: Design of activity toolkit (updates).
 - Task 6.2: Design of activities AND Task 6.3: Implementation of activities (later cycles).
 - Task 6.4: Collection of activity artefacts (later cycles).

Deliverables

- The following deliverable was produced in this reporting period:
 - D6.2. Second cycle Activity Toolkit.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the collection of the research artefacts. MS13 was reached in M18 (even if the delivery of the complete report was on M20). MS14 suffered a delay, due to the difficulties in collecting the proofs of evidence from the young learners delivering the projects. MS14 was reached at the end of the project.

1.2.6.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

During the research cycle, the focus was on establishing the teams and getting the members to collaborate, facilitating relationships, determining the roles within the project teams, and moving the team to the point where they started to collaborate effectively and efficiently. In addition, project partners contributed to sustain the projects and monitored that there would be a clear output and tangible deliverables. However, it would be an added value to observe the dedication of the participants in their drive to change the world and make their voices heard, in order to gain qualitative data.

One of the greatest benefits of this cycle was to provide an opportunity to participants to create and design projects based on their abilities and interests. By working on creative projects, participants clearly showed progress in their research and organisation skills, while feeling responsible and self-motivated to gain the skills needed in the Digital Age. Although the duration of the projects changed according to the content and research methods, it was obvious that long-term projects provided individual learning opportunities tailored to their growth and academic achievement. The projects provided the participants with meaningful choices in a relevant context, and valuable learning time to make sense of the information gathered and processed. The immediate feedback received on an individual basis supported their learning. Those outcomes provided an immediate, tangible satisfaction to participants, as well as two positive proof-points: on the one hand, they confirmed the creative potential of young learners and on the other served as a marketing story to spread the message of WYRED.

The Activity Toolkit is a valuable element within the WYRED approach. It serves as a useful reference guide and support for participants in the WYRED approach, with a useful and accessible diversity of approaches that can fit a wide range of contexts. It constitutes an interesting conversation point in valorisation conversations, particularly where these are exploring the viability of the WYRED approach in new domains.

1.2.7 Work package 7: EVALUATION AND INTERPRETATION PHASE

WP7 began on May 2017 (M7 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project (estimated end in DoA M34). WP7 Leader is PYE. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.7.1 WP Highlights

The aim of WP 7 intends to provide useful tools for both young participants and adults to help young participants reflect on their research process and outputs, share the results from their work and inspire them on how to present it in a creative and meaningful way. It also facilitates self-assessment for participants to reflect about the activities they have just done and how they have affected them.

In the second period of the project this work has undergone some evolution as Working Group 4 which focuses on the WYRED research cycle, has worked to streamline the cycle and facilitate the evaluation and interpretation work that brings WYRED outputs to the attention of policy and other decision makers, as well as the wider society.

The focus of the partners was also linked to exploiting all opportunities of sharing the research results through key outlets.

1. The sharing of research findings and their interpretation by the children and young people was the platform space itself. As the artefacts were produced and the projects were concluded, the facilitators supported the participants to upload their work to the WYRED platform. Because this space was built and designed to allow for safe and secure interaction, all WYRED participants who were engaged within the platform had already accessed here in a facilitated manner. Conversations and community interactions continued here with the support of the facilitators. Children and young people have the option to indicate the level of viewing access.

2. A second key focal point for the sharing of WYRED results, as well as creating a space for their shared interpretation and analysis was through the public space of the WYRED website. The WYRED project participants shared summaries of their projects and facilitators uploaded documentation that presented overviews of results. As this is a public

3. At a third level, in order to draw together the variety of outcomes generated in the WYRED research projects and to make them more easily accessible a summary document, the WYRED Insights report, was created. This document has been produced on an annual basis to date to give an overview of the insights and outputs generated by the work of the young people in WYRED, at all stages of the cycle. This document is not an official deliverable (though available for review) but it is one of the more important outputs particularly from the sustainability perspective and will continue to be produced by the WYRED Association.

netWorked Youth Research for
Empowerment in the Digital society

WYRED INSIGHTS REPORT 2019

1750 children and young
people involved in the
project

The WYRED project was funded through the Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation programme. The project provides a space for children and young people to engage in reflection about their digital lives. Over the course of the three year project, the nine partners have guided over 1750 children and young people to ask questions and carry out research about themes and ideas that affect and shape their interactive, performative and communicative worlds with especial focus on subjects relating to the digital society. Through these efforts, the children and young people have navigated and explored aspects of an ever evolving landscape where their experience of growing up and maturing has been in many ways mediated by technological developments and experiments. Through WYRED, the partners have listened carefully and remained tuned into their critical analysis, but the emphasis has been on the autonomy of the young participants to define their agenda and direct their own exploration.

These three focal points for the sharing and interpretation of WYRED results have acted as very successful highlights of the second phase of the project.

1.2.7.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

The work has been coordinated by PYE, and all partners have contributed with recommendations and feedback to the work of WP7 and their direct experience of working with the different groups of children and young people. The input from the facilitators also have been vital elements in streamlining the processes. and reporting templates used.

Partners were committed to ongoing evaluation, which was also critical to the success of WYRED activities. From initial phases, partners worked together to collect data and evidence on how children and young people in each country have experienced and engaged within each methodological step.

TELL US SOMETHING ABOUT YOUR JOURNEY...	
Who would you like to tell about your journey? List 4 or 5 examples, also with images for each scenario A friend family <u>class mates/group of friends</u> to everybody	
Show them the movie	
If you had a microphone and the whole world was listening, what is the most important thing you would like to tell them about what you discovered on your journey? (What message would you tell them?) Cyberbullying is hurtful and is a wrong thing to do	
How will you explain all these adventures? Imagine that you are back home and you want to explain this journey - what would be the best way you could share what you discovered with others? Use the materials you have been collecting during your research process (photos, videos, texts, music, etc) and do these activities to choose the best support/way to explain your research.	
Show the movie on Wured Platform	
Online exercises: - blank postcard: design your own image and send a message about your research	Offline sessions with facilitators: - Song & rhythm - Pass the poem - Sensitivity line - storytelling

Partners supported each other in the review and updating of self-evaluation tools. Evaluation toolkits have been designed to allow the voices of children and young people to emerge. Project results are shared and discussed through the WYRED platform

1.2.7.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Together with WP5 and WP6, this WP formed part of the WYRED as research Working Group (4) and the work done between these WPs was instrumental in streamlining the WYRED approach, and particularly bringing together reporting and evaluation processes into a simpler process.

PYE collaborated closely with all partners to develop and test this new template (based on the reporting already completed in earlier cycles). Once the final version was agreed, this was used extensively and allowed for the development of an aggregated dataset, from which reports could be extracted and analysed by all partners according to need. The template now used collects information from throughout the cycle and brings it together in one place, which greatly facilitates the reflection processes that form part of the process of deciding how and with whom to share the outputs of their work.

While the initial project design focused on using Cycle 1 and 2 to inform the iterative development of the evaluation processes, it was decided to extend the coverage of deliverables 7.3, 7.4 and 7.6 to greater use of the results and project activity data.

With this in mind, deliverable 7.3 included feedback and results from Cycle 2 (especially in the development of a suite of case studies) as well as Cycle 1 to make for a more detailed and comprehensive overview of the work to date. . The specific case studies included:

- Boundaries- How can yoga help young people in the digital age?
- Doga- Democracy in Schools
- Early Years Organisation- “Children Examining “Fake” News”
- MOVES- “Reflections on My Life”
- OIT- “Responding to Globalisation and Self-Representation in the Digital Society

- PYE- “Housing and homelessness within our community”
- TAU- “How to shape a better future for Israeli society”
- USAL- “Globalisation, the nation and the individual in today's world”
- YEU- “Brave New You”

In a similar manner, later deliverables 7.4 and 7.6 included considerable analysis of Cycle 3 activity to inform these reports. These conclusions and recommendations are being strengthened given the increased access to partner level data. This analysis also provided input into the second Insights Report.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

- Task 7.1: Overall evaluation approach.
- Task 7.2: Implement evaluations across the research activities (later cycles).
- Task 7.3: Evaluation reports (later cycles).
- Task 7.4: Recommendations formats (videos/reports/artefacts).

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

- D7.4 Second cycle Evaluation report.
- D7.6 Second Cycle Recommendations collection.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the collection of the Recommendations. MS15 was reached in M18, while MS 16 suffered a delay in order to incorporate Cycle 3 and was reached at the end of the project. A further delay was experienced in completing D7.4 and D7.6, as partners extended their Cycle 3 activities to fit in line with the timing of the Online Festival.

1.2.7.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

Despite the importance of reporting in WYRED as part of the process of reflection on what has been done it is not a particularly interesting activity for most participants. The development of an integrated template across all partners that covered all reporting activities (including social dialogues, research questions, artefacts and evaluations) allowed for a more streamlined and cohesive approach to reporting during Cycle 3 and has been invaluable in lightening the workload related to reporting.

As part of the analysis phase of the research cycle, partners worked to extract relevant thematic lessons from the activity base and project work. Their focus in this regard was to look at the future potential of the methodology. A number of important insights were drawn out to stress core WYRED lessons:

- Children and young people have generated understanding regarding the importance of developing coping mechanisms and understanding resilience from a young age
- Such life-skills can then allow the child or young person to develop their online identity and relationships within their digital life in a positive manner
- Creative approaches to promoting learning and developing a voice are supported by the WYRED framework

Another key lesson learned relates to the importance of linking outputs to valorisation and networking. The second period of WYRED has involved a progressive deepening of this integrated work and linkage between outputs and valorisation, and the more results emerging from the cycles the easier and more fluid the valorisation work came to be.

The production of the Insights reports as well as the recommendations reports allowed for clarity of purpose when examining next steps for the WYRED Association. Partner feedback was collated on a regular basis and difference versions of these tools were developed for different audiences.

1.2.8 Work package 8: VALORISATION

WP8 began on November 2016 (M1 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. WP8 Leader is OXFAM. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.8.1 WP Highlights

Oxfam Italia has led WP 8 and has been especially responsible for facilitating and articulating the valorisation work, namely WYRED's activity on an international level in order to ensure maximum impact and the European reach of the project. Valorisation has been a central part of the WYRED project and fundamental in terms of its sustainability. From the beginning of the project, the consortium has aimed at setting up and strengthening a WYRED community by building awareness and engaging people into the work on the platform.

Valorising and disseminating WYRED's activity were gradual in the first 18 months as it has followed the whole cycle process, which included network building through Delphi questionnaires, stakeholder mapping, social dialogues and the ensuing research activities which generated recommendations of different kinds (and formats) to policy and decision makers and other social sectors. The second 18 months, however, saw a shift not only in disseminating and valorising WYRED's activities but also in the partners' vision and strategy to strengthen WYRED in terms of visibility, stakeholder engagement and sustainability.

The main highlights of WYRED's valorisation can be summarized as follows:

- Creating a common Valorisation Plan (D8.1) (WYRED Consortium, 2017a), which focused on three main areas, namely: valorisation, dissemination and exploitation. The Valorisation Plan identified exploitation and dissemination target groups, tangible and intangible dissemination products, dissemination distribution channel and tools such as WYRED's visual identity and the technological infrastructure to support the dissemination work. Last of all, the Valorisation Plan outlined the exploitation strategy needed to lever change, including the Showcase Workshops and set up of the WYRED Association. The Valorisation Plan was revised at the end of the first year and updated with the second year's Valorisation Plan (D8.2) (WYRED Consortium, 2018) considering a review of the first year's progress and limits and necessary planning for the second year.
- The website <https://wyredproject.eu/> and social media infrastructure provided by the project coordinator have supported publication and 7 blogs in each of the partner languages as well as a global blog in English and an automated system for the generation of newsletters.
- Institutional repository of GRIAL group at the University of Salamanca

<https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/722> (154 documents), Public community in Zenodo, for visibility/interoperability with the EU OpenAire initiative. <https://zenodo.org/communities/wyred> (121 documents).

- Visibility and stakeholder engagement. Through the website, partners increased WYRED's visibility and stakeholder engagement by integrating two important sections: Stories <https://wyredproject.eu/category/stories/> and conversations <https://wyredproject.eu/international-conversations/> which both gave Children and Young People a place to share and articulate their opinions on relevant issues. These conversations led on to the WYRED Online Festival <https://wyredproject.eu/online-festival/> which was held at the very end of the project so as bring in new and more stakeholders, and to capture important insights for policy makers as well as a place to launch the WYRED Association.
- The WYRED Association was set up with its articles and board members, registered in Austria and is now up and running open for new members to join, thus guaranteeing the projects' legacy and sustainability.

1.2.8.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

All partners have been key to guarantee WP8 and have had tasks to contribute to valorising, disseminating and exploiting WYRED. In accordance to the Valorisation Plan, all partners were asked to fill in and share a Valorisation Report List every 4 months in order to be able to collect all of WYRED's activities, including evidence which is crucial for monitoring impact. Oxfam Italia facilitated this harvesting process, which it then systematised in the Valorisation Reports, deliverable D8.6 at the end of the first year and D8.7 in the second year and D8.8 in the third year. In addition to feeding the international blog in English, all partners were also responsible for updating their country online blogs as well as translating any relevant news into or from their language and English, which is the common language in WYRED.

In collaboration with WP5, the Social Dialogue Session Report Form was revised in M12 so as to include a summary of the social dialogue session which could be shared via a post on the international blog. In M19 a decision was made for the consortium to work differently, gathering stories from the activities being implemented in a template provided by Oxfam Italia. These stories were regularly provided by different partners following a set calendar. In the run up to the project meeting in M19, partners also received and were asked to contribute to developing an updated stakeholder engagement strategy, which was co-created between WP 8 and WP 7 leaders.

1.2.8.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Valorisation was organised into its own separate work package, but much of the activity involved in other work packages such as building the network (WP4) and social dialogues (WP5) but also all other WP's where stakeholders were involved strictly translates into valorising, disseminating and exploiting WYRED. It is for this reason, that a shared understanding of the Valorisation Plan in terms of it being cross cutting to most of the WP's as well as good coordination between partners, facilitated by Oxfam Italia has been important. This process has been revised throughout the course of the project's duration and complimentary ways of working across all the WP's were set up in the run up to the project meeting in Bath in M19 and also following on from the indications received from the Technical Review Report. Four working groups (WG) were set up between partners irrelevant of their WP lead:

- WG 1 the scope of WYRED.
- WG 2 the WYRED space.

- WG3 WYRED and society.
- WG4 WYRED as research.

Task 8.2, public website and social media presence, of WP 8 was implemented and once again proved fundamental to WYRED's development. The public website was created early in the project <https://wyredproject.eu/> and has functioned as the public front-end of the WYRED platform, providing a continuous flow of news and inputs around the project's activity and pertinent youth issues. Extensive and active social media were integrated into the website and have been used to attract participants to the network.

WYRED's Social media accounts:

- <https://www.facebook.com/wyredeuproject>
- <https://twitter.com/wyredeuproject>
- <https://instagram.com/wyredeuproject>
- <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYUj-1xXd9332sVFhh3DFJg>

Oxfam Italia promoted and monitored Task 8.3: Events, through its Valorisation Progress Reports. Throughout the project, the consortium participated in events organised in the different partner countries or internationally. The principal strategy was mainly to partner with other youth events, rather than competing, and focus on engaging through the online component especially.

The flagship event was [3-day Online WYRED Festival](#). It had originally been planned to hold this event yearly, however early in the second period it was decided to have a more extensive three-day event at the end of the project that would give the project momentum to carry it into the post-funding period. The WYRED Online Festival lasted for 3 days, from 22nd to 24th October 2019, and drew together all the elements of WYRED activity during the second period. Participation was free of charge and hosted on the "Zoom" platform, Participants could connect at any time following a specific link for each day published on the festival page <https://wyredproject.eu/online-festival>. The structure of the WYRED online festival was dynamic including a mix of WYRED and new project presentations, talks, round tables, Q&A's (questions and answers) video competitions and webinars. At the end of each of the three days, policy recommendations were drawn out of C&YP's presentations and contributions and shared with all those participating. These and other significant insights from WYRED are captured in the Insights Report. In this event, as well as providing a forum for participants in WYRED to share their projects and insights. the WYRED partners involved many relevant stakeholders including three MEPs (Brando Benifei, Evin Incir both from S&D group and Irena Joveva-Renew Europe), the Children's Commissioner from Northern Ireland, representatives of the Advisory Council on Youth of Council of Europe, Prof. Helle Rootzen DTU - Professor in Learning Technology and Digitalisation and head of learnT DTU Copenhagen, Maria Giulia Ballatore (Politecnico di Torino, Italy), Davina Bibiella (GEOMAR, Germany), Nicole Liddell (CIVIC, United Kingdom), Merve Yorulmaz (Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Germany), Ileana María Greca Dufranc (University of Burgos, Spain) and Bettina Enzenhofer (Technische Universität Wien, Austria). The event was well attended with different classrooms connecting at different moments according to their interest and availability. There were useful and valuable discussions and a range of recommendations were generated (captured in the Insights report) and the recordings will furthermore be used by the WYRED Association going forward.

Since the impact indicators for social media were defined in the proposal there has been a shift in the way social media can be measured. At that time the number of followers was paramount, but increasingly people may view a video or share a tweet without necessarily becoming a follower. Instagram stories or tweets on Twitter have a range of visibility that is not measured in followers, but the impact and the dissemination of the information occurs. For example, a tweet can have 500 impressions (times people saw the tweet on Twitter) and only 20 are from followers. Regarding YouTube, people usually watch videos but do not subscribe to the channel, so the viewers usually are not reflected in an increase of the subscription to the channel. The aim was to have 3000 social media followers, but though our numbers are lower (around 500 “followers”) we estimate our reach through the different social channels and those signed up to our own platform to be of that order.

The stakeholder engagement showcase-workshops (Task 8.4) were implemented by partners in their national contexts during the second period, after Cycle 1 had been fully completed, which had a slight delay.

Task 8.5 was the WYRED Association set up. This task has been fundamental to ensure the sustainability of the WYRED platform and activity for the future after EU funding ends, when a different model for the funding of the activity will be required. A first version of the WYRED Association Business Plan was drafted in M17 which the Consortium discussed prior to the Project Meeting due in Bath, UK in M19. A definite version of WP8_D8.4 was submitted in M23. At the end of the project, the WYRED Association is set up, based in Austria, and ready to take WYRED forward into the next phase of its existence. Finally, Oxfam Italia has implemented Task 8.6: three Valorisation reports, one for each year.

There are several scientific publications related to WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016c, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) and specifically with the WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018, 2019; García-Peñalvo, 2016b; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo et al., 2018; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, García-Holgado, & Seoane-Pardo, 2019). All the scientific publications are available in open access (Ramírez-Montoya & García-Peñalvo, 2015; Ramírez-Montoya, García-Peñalvo, & McGreal, 2018) in the institutional repository of the coordinator partner (<https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/723>), the WYRED Community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/wyred>), and in the WYRED public web portal (<https://wyredproject.eu/publications/>). In numbers, WYRED scientific publication means 5 papers in journals and 11 papers in conferences. Moreover, 1 PhD thesis and 3 Master theses are related or done in the scope of WYRED project.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 8.2: Public website and social media presence.

Task 8.3: Events.

Task 8.4: Stakeholders engagement showcase workshops.

Task 8.5: WYRED association set up.

Task 8.6 Valorisation reports.

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

- D8.3: Year 1 Valorisation Plan.
- D8.7: Year 2 Valorisation Report.
- D8.8: Year 3 Valorisation Report.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the WYRED Association set up. MS17 was reached in M18 as regards the elaboration of a draft version of the Association Business plan and Articles shared among the partners and discussed in the project meeting in Bath (June 2018). The version of D8.4 delivered in M18 was rejected by the evaluators, who considered the plan not realistic. An updated version was submitted on September 2018 (M23), as required. The Association was established in Austria and is fully operative.

1.2.8.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

Following the Technical Review Report, the Consortium, led by Oxfam learnt that it should scale up dissemination efforts so as to keep WYRED moving forward. There was a strong recommendation, shared by Oxfam Italia, for the team to strategically enhance its valorisation efforts. The consortium needed to find creative ways to 1) attract those most vulnerable to know of and contribute to the project, 2) find suitable pathways and actors to meet its diverse target group where (and in the manners in which) they actually are active and vocal in the digital sphere, 3) include all those voices in the ongoing and relevant empowerment international and national dialogues, actions and policy-making. As a result, a task force (Working Group 3: WYRED and Society) was set up and addressed several factors and action points, distributing tasks were necessary. One significant change that occurred in year 2 and subsequently improved WYRED's impact as well as the partners' ways of valorisation was to narrow the focus of WYRED based on the Delphi findings and youth trends as previously mentioned.

These themes then became the basis of conversations, which were set up to engage C&YP and other stakeholders in/through WYRED. These conversations also led up to the WYRED Online Festival which was structured around these same six themes.

Some highlights from the policy recommendations on Day 1 regarding Information and Internet Safety:

- We should have laws specific to being on the internet and its own police force.
- The internet can be as scary, as exciting, as useful and as a waste of time as you want it to be taken control of your actions!
- On cyberbullying: behave as you would in the real world; remember the Netiquette! If you don't have anything nice to say, don't say anything.
- On being safe: behave as you would in the real world! The 'internet' is not a person you can trust! Learn about security settings, cover your webcam, etc.
- On digital footprint: 'They' know what they know because you tell them! Learn about cookies, privacy settings, etc. What goes online, stays online – forever!
- On fake news: beware of the 'echo chamber' effect; use various sources to triangulate data, use critical thinking.

Some highlights from the policy recommendations on Day 2 regarding Gender and Self Image:

- STEAM-Based Classroom Projects.

- STEM Equity Legislation.
- All-Girl STEM Organisations.
- Targeted Grants and Fellowships.
- Capabilities-deepen skills and competences.
- Careers- pathways.
- Building a STEM identity.
- Format of teaching and learning matters.

Some highlights from the policy recommendations on Day 3 regarding Digital Participation and Living on Social Media:

- Urgent legislation is required for Social Media corporations to safeguard people's privacy (e.g., stricter background checks for the compliance of GDPR within social media channels).
- Urgent legislation is required for Social Media corporations to have limited power (including marketing, publicity, politics, etc).
- Individuals should have the right to take down (for good) information posted.
- Schools and Universities need to approach and use (teach) digital tools and online spaces more safely, implementing media literacy educational programmes in the school curricula for young people.
- Stricter parental control for children under 12 when navigating the web.
- There should be access available for all young people around the world to the information found on the web.

To conclude, the WYRED Association was set up and is currently running. <https://association.wyredproject.eu/> Members can join the Association as individuals or as associations, bodies, organisations, networks, etc. The WYRED Association's structure and objectives have been articulated in the Business Plan and Articles (D8.4 and D8.5). All WYRED partners are part of the Association and have been responsible for bringing in new members. The WYRED Association will foresee that the project's legacy continues and will hopefully evolve to create new opportunities for C&YP to voice their opinions about how digital society shapes their lives. It will also provide a space for research and policy that can attract those who write the rules in society.

1.2.9 Work package 9: PROJECT MANAGEMENT

WP9 began on November 2016 (M1 of the project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project and, after that, during the final reporting preparation. WP9 Leader is USAL. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.9.1 WP Highlights

WP9 Project Management included monitoring the progress of all work done and the budget and resources used and ensuring the timely completion of deliverables.

The WYRED consortium was made up of nine partners, a number which is manageable with an agile and relatively lean structure, and so operational management has been carried out in a collaborative way in accordance with the precepts of good governance and the usual operational procedures of each organisation in such a way as to ensure timely and appropriate participation in the activities assigned to the organisation and the achievement of the objectives of the project. Throughout the project the coordinating partner, and the WP leaders, monitored progress,

carried out risk assessment and flagged any issues for discussion at the regular project meetings. The applicant and partners provided detailed financial report of their activities, providing evidences of costs as per financial and administrative requirements.

A Project Handbook with guidelines and reporting templates for the proper and effective management was created at the beginning of the project and progress reports were delivered to facilitate, gather and collate the information required for monitoring resource consumption and project achievement annually, and create reports for submission to the Commission (open meeting, review meeting and periodic report).

In the second 18 months of the Project:

- 28 deliverables were expected to be submitted and all of them have been released.
- 13 milestones were set and achieved.
- Four international project meetings were held.
- All the partners received the second instalment by October 2018.

The management structure has been mainly designed to:

- Effectively facilitate and manage the interaction of the different groups in the Project.
- Successfully integrate different backgrounds from research, young people and technical environments.
- Ensure that the generated data along the Project is quality controlled and effectively exploited.

The management structure included the following key roles: Project coordinator, Steering Committee, Management Committee, Youth Panel, WP leaders and Ethics Advisory Board. The profile, role and responsibilities are described in the Consortium Agreement [CA – Section 6] [GA – Annex I Part B – 2.3.2 Management structure and procedures].

Communication and collaboration have worked well within the project with an increasing degree of commitment shown by the partners in particular in the second half of the project, also thanks to the shift to an organization by working groups, that has helped to reduce the sense of fragmentation that existed before. The difficulties especially due to changes of personnel in some teams have been resolved appropriately.

In presence transnational project meetings

During the 3 years all the 7 project meetings were held: the kick-off right at the beginning of the project, a mid-year meeting and a meeting to close the first year and prepare the next stages and a meeting before the delivery of the mid-term report at M20. The meetings in Istanbul and Belfast were devoted to review the project implementation and to organize the valorisation and internationalization activities. The final meeting was an occasion for the last input from the advisory board and to fix the last activities, included the reporting to the Commission.

The scheduling of the meetings followed the calendar both as regards the locations and the dates.

Meeting Location	Date	Project Month	Partners that participated	Purpose of the meeting
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Salamanca (ES)	November 2 nd – 3 rd , 2016	M1	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	To develop an initial shared understanding of the project and of the processes involved, centred on definitions, expectations, and challenges
Vienna (AT)	May 29 th – 31 st , 2017	M7	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	To have a review of the project implementation during the first 6 months, to present the first release of the platform and to take decisions about next tasks' plan
Florence (IT)	November 13 th -15 th , 2017	M13	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	To share results and personal and organisational expectations and challenges towards the project, to analyse national strategies in engaging youth and stakeholders through project's activities, to provide a reflection based on lesson learned and future steps.
Bath (UK)	June 18 th - 20 th , 2018	M20	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	To have a face to face meeting with the Advisory Board To examine specific issues, we have identified that need work, and plan specific actions, according to the working groups reports. Discussions about sustainability and the WYRED Association

Istanbul (Turkey)	November 20th - 21st, 2018	M25	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	<p>To have a face to face meeting with the Advisory Board</p> <p>To reflect on WYRED Insights, streamlining the cycle, and internationalization activities. Discussions about sustainability and the WYRED Association</p>
Belfast (UK)	March 11 th -13 th , 2019	M29	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	<p>To share information about the Working Groups' work, especially Online schedule and Festival preparations. Conversations and reporting template.</p> <p>Discussions about sustainability and the WYRED Association</p> <p>Meeting with Northern Ireland Commissioner for Children and Young People Koulla Yiasouma.</p>
Brussels (BE)	September 4 th -6 th , 2019	M35	1 or 2 representatives of each institution	<p>To have a face to face meeting with the Advisory Board</p> <p>To prepare the WYRED online festival and to review the last activities planned before the project closure. Discussions about sustainability and the WYRED Association</p> <p>To check the steps for preparing the final reporting.</p>

The approach to the meetings' organization (agenda, spaces, methodology, etc.) has positively evolved along the seven moments, with an increasing involvement and participation of all the

partners. In Bath, Istanbul and Brussels a day was devoted to have a meeting with the Advisory Board.

Online project meetings

Date	Project Month	Topics of the meeting
September 16 th , 2016	Before the project started	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction round • Overview of the project • Management and financial issues • Kick-off meeting organization
January 25 th , 2017	M3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1_WYRED processes: monitoring D1.1 • Comments on progress in WP2, WP4 and WP8 • Management and financial issues: Project Handbook (D9.1), Consortium Agreement and Quality Plan • 2nd meeting date
February 22 nd , 2017	M4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closure of deliverables pending D1.1, D1.4, D4.1, D4.5, D8.1 • Comments on progress in WP4 (manifesto, stakeholder contacts, slogan competition, video and training actions) • WYRED website • Information about the 2nd meeting organization
March 29 th , 2017	M5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of the Delphi activity (TAU and BOUNDARIES) • Preparation of the Social Dialogues (EARLY YEARS and BOUNDARIES) • Report on WP4 Stakeholder questionnaire (MOVES, all partners) • Report on WP4 networking actions (YEI, all partners)
April 26 th , 2017	M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive instructions about the Delphi implementation (TAU and BOUNDARIES) • Guidelines for the Social Dialogues (EARLY YEARS and BOUNDARIES)
May 8 th , 2017	M7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check on the status of the Delphi implementation (TAU) • Guidelines for the Social Dialogues (EARLY YEARS and BOUNDARIES) • Slogan competition (OXFAM)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vienna meeting agenda (MOVES and USAL)
October 10 th , 2017	M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of the in-presence meeting in Florence
April 3 rd , 2018	M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 2 “The WYRED space” meeting
April 16 th , 2018	M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 1 “The scope of WYRED” meeting
March 23 rd , 2018	M17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 3 “WYRED and society” meeting
April 4 th , 2018	M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 3 “WYRED and society” meeting
April 16 th , 2018	M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 4 “WYRED as research” meeting
May 25 th , 2018	M19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 2 “The WYRED space” meeting
September 28 th , 2018	M23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 3 “WYRED and society” meeting
November 17 th , 2018	M25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 2 “The WYRED space” meeting.
December 19 th , 2018	M26	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working Group 3 “WYRED and society” meeting
January 14 th , 2019	M27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
February 11 th , 2019	M28	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
April 8 th , 2019	M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
April 9 th , 2019	M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parallel meetings to coordinate the WYRED Online Festival activities.

May 13th, 2019	M31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
June 10th, 2019	M32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
July 8th, 2019	M33	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.
September 4th, 2019	M34	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the activities associated to all Working Groups.

During the third year the organization of the skype meetings was more regular. A monthly coordination meeting of all working groups was planned. Moreover, there were online meetings organized as part of particular tasks (international conversations, online festival, inclusion, platform development, networking, etc.), they are documented in the relevant reports.

Implementation of the workplan:

According to the project proposal, the WYRED project was designed to work in cycles (WYRED Consortium, 2017b, 2017c) with 10 work packages involved in the project work plan.

The plan originally intended two full iterations of the WYRED cycle during the funding period, however it was considered that it would be valuable to carry out three cycles completely over the three years. After the funding period, cycles will continue indefinitely under the aegis of the WYRED Association.

The processes described in the deliverables associated to each WP, and the outcomes produced reflect the results of the implementation of the

- WYRED 1st cycle (December 2016, M2 – February 2017, M15),
- WYRED 2nd cycle (July 2017, M9 – August 2018, M22)
- WYRED 3rd cycle (September 2018, M23 – August 2019, M34).

The 3rd cycle, not originally anticipated, was implemented during the 3rd project year and products and results of this cycle have been included in the deliverables originally devoted to the description and analysis of the 2nd cycle results.

This meant that WYRED activities continued right through to the end of the funding period, and the WYRED online festival took place from 22nd to 24th October 2019 (<https://wyredproject.eu/online-festival/>). Though this has delayed the production of some deliverables, it has provided useful momentum to carry through to the post-funding period, and the Festival was a success for the project in terms of increasing the impact of the activities.

Risk management:

Risk management followed the Critical Implementation risks and mitigation actions defined in GA – Annex I Part A, section 1.3.5 WT5, “Critical Implementation risks and mitigation actions”. No significant risk situations appeared during R2.

1.2.9.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

USAL, as lead partner for WP9, was in charge of the overall approach and monitoring of the project management. Partners were involved in WP9 by ensuring the implementation of the tasks and providing input to the management procedures.

The roles and responsibilities that were introduced in the Project Handbook D9.1 and in the Consortium agreement have been maintained throughout the three years.

1.2.9.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

The work was implemented appropriately and in time.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 9.1: Project management guidelines and reporting templates.

Task 9.2: Project meetings.

Task 9.3: Annual reports (public/private).

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

D9.3. Year 2 Annual report.

D9.4. Year 3 Annual report.

Milestones

The milestones in this WP relate to the Annual Reports, so MS18, MS19 and MS20 have been achieved with the delivery of the relevant reports.

1.2.9.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

The description of processes and outcomes implemented during the WYRED project 3rd year confirm a solid project with a good management infrastructure.

The challenges faced in the first year were overcome and the third year addressed positively the impact-related challenges that had been identified both inside the WYRED platform and in the face to face events. The consortium used the recommendations arising from the EU review report, the internal quality monitoring and from the meetings with the advisory board to make adjustments and reach the project objectives.

1.2.1 Work Package 10: QUALITY MANAGEMENT

WP1 began on November 2016 (MI of the Project) and since then it has been active until the end of the project. WP1 Leader is BOUNDARIES. All partners contributed to the activities of the WP.

1.2.10.1 WP Highlights

WP10 focused on the evaluation of the WYRED project as a project, focusing on project processes such as partner communication, collaboration and reporting and other issues. It also examined partner perceptions of the success of the project and its outputs. The evaluation throughout was understood as formative, its aim being to help the project improve and better achieve its aims. This continued throughout the second period of the project and though some elements of summative evaluation entered at the end of the project the focus has continued even in the final evaluation on improvement, in this latter case with a view to sustainability in the post-funding period. There was good collaboration with WP1 within Working Group 1 which

focused on the scope of WYRED, indeed this work generated the original idea of an Insights report as a potential key part of the scope of the approach.

There were three main dimensions to the work in WP10; internal processes managed with the partners, an external advisory board which met periodically with the partners to discuss the progress of the project and suggest improvements, and an ethical dimension which comprised two independent Ethical Reviews to ensure ethical issues were taken into account throughout the project in line with the provisions of the Participant Protection Policy document.

The internal processes proceeded throughout the project according to plan. The final Quality and Evaluation report was produced at the very end of the project. These processes functioned appropriately and did help the consortium to reflect on progress and make the necessary adjustments as the project progressed.

As mentioned in the previous report, the second dimension of the work package, the Advisory Board suffered some delays in the first period, but in the second period the meetings were back on schedule and this dimension of the work package proved very useful, providing external perspectives on the work that were very valuable in helping to orient the work towards sustainability especially.

The ethical dimension contained one internal process, the Ethical Advisory Board, which was planned to meet only when there was a perceived issue to deal with. This did not take place during the project. This was an independent external ethical review process, which took place twice, with different reviewers as the first was unable to continue for the second review. This had however the advantage of providing a further perspective. Neither reviewer identified issues either and the reviews were positive, giving us confidence about the ethical dimension of the project.

1.2.10.2 Distribution of tasks among partners

BOUNDARIES was the lead partner for Work Package 10 and was in charge of design and implementation of quality control procedures and the overall approach, liaising with the coordinator. Partners were involved in WP10 by providing their input and perceptions to evaluation procedures.

1.2.10.3 WP progress (tasks implementation, main activities and outcomes)

Apart from the already mentioned delays in the constitution of the Advisory Board, the work was implemented appropriately and served its purpose, aiding the partners to reflect on the work and providing timely commentary to guide the process throughout the project.

Tasks

The following tasks were implemented during this reporting period:

Task 10.2: Advisory Board.

Task 10.3: Annual evaluation/quality reports.

Task 10.5: Independent external ethical review.

Deliverables

The following deliverables were produced in this reporting period:

D10.5. Advisory Board meeting 4

D10.6. Advisory Board meeting 5

D10.7. Advisory Board meeting 6

- D10.9. Yearly 2 Quality and Evaluation Annual report
- D10.10. Yearly 3 Quality and Evaluation Annual report
- D10.12. Final Independent Ethical Review (M36): delivered (M36)

Milestones

The milestones in this WP related to the Annual Quality and Evaluation Reports. MS21, MS22 and MS23 were achieved with the delivery of the relevant reports.

1.2.10.4 Lessons learned, relevance of the research, and exploitable results

The function of the work in WP10 was to support the consortium in achieving the objectives of WYRED. The three dimensions, internal, external and ethical, complemented each other and helped to provide a full picture of the situation at any given time.

A lesson learned in relation to this work was the degree to which deliverables, though necessary, provide a punctuated view of specific moments. The same is true of WPS which can easily lead to “silo” patterns of work. As the project shifted to an organisation based principally on working groups focusing on the key dimensions of the project, evaluation necessarily became a continuous process, that was embedded in the day to day work.

The key insight emerging from all the evaluation dimensions has been the paradox of an approach that is highly valued, once experienced, but often not understood prior to participation. The evaluation work has contributed extensively to reflection of the need for the streamlining of the approach to make it more flexible and accessible, and the result of this is that the approach is now much more easily comprehensible than it was originally. In this sense the work of WP10 has played an important role in making the results of the project more exploitable and the WYRED approach more sustainable.

1.3 Impact

Include in this section whether the information on section 2.1 of the DoA (how your project will contribute to the expected impacts) is still relevant or needs to be updated. Include further details in the latter case.

The information provided in section 2.1 of the DoA remains relevant. Though our thinking about the nature of the impacts of WYRED evolved along the project, particularly in terms of our understanding of the nature of engagement, we are already seeing evidence of impacts of the kinds we described there.

2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of result (if applicable)

Include in this section whether the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.

The DoA described a strategy that involved a valorisation plan (covering exploitation and dissemination and communication) that was updated annually, and to a large extent superseded the more general description in the DoA. That said, the overall plan described in the DoA served as a useful set of broad guidelines that oriented the work, and therefore did not need to be updated. However, at the level of day to day dissemination and exploitation activity the latest version of the Valorisation plan (updated yearly) had always undergone some adjustment. In particular at the beginning of the third year and as a result of the insights of the EC reviewers in their technical report of M18 a working group, called WYRED and society, was created

which brought together all the work in the project that looked outward - principally networking, dissemination, stakeholder interaction, exploitation and sustainability - and coordinated all this activity to maximum effect. This work has been described in detail in the Year 2 Valorisation report, and the insights from it incorporated into the Year 3 Plan.

3. Update of the data management plan (if applicable)

Include in this section whether the data management plan as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.

The data management plans were covered in the current version of the Participant Protection Policy (version 4 of the plan D1.7 was the last one). The considerations in the DoA were still relevant and broad guidelines and did not require updating.

4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable)

Include in this section the list of recommendations and comments from previous reviews and give information on how they have been followed up.

The previous review made a series of recommendations regarding current work.

The first of these related to the **Advisory Board**. D10.2 remained outstanding and was therefore rejected. Since then it, and the other two related deliverables (D10.3 and D10.4) have been completed and uploaded. The work of the Advisory Board since then was on schedule and providing valuable input.

With regard to the **Manifesto**, the aim was to revisit this aspect of the project as part of the activity on the WYRED platform. The manifesto has always been understood as part of the engagement process and it has been used in this way.

Reflections on **Research Cycle Phase 1**, and the potential narrowing of focus have been applied with very good results. The project adopted four main areas of focus in order to address the recommendations and carry the work forward. These were addressed through Working Groups that cut across the related WPs and look to make the activity more agile. Each of the Working Groups addressed one or more of the recommendations.

5. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)

Explain the reasons for deviations from the DoA, the consequences and the proposed corrective actions.

5.1 Tasks

Include explanations for tasks not fully implemented, critical objectives not fully achieved and/or not being on schedule. Explain also the impact on other tasks on the available resources and the planning.

Deviations suffered by the project during the first year (the timing between countries in cycle 1, the delay in the platform implementation and Advisory Board set up) and reported in R1 have been successfully addressed and solved.

The project was back on schedule. The infrastructure from M19 was fully in place and the lessons learned from the first cycle implemented, so the project achieved its objectives.

5.2 Use of resources (not applicable for MSCA)

Include explanations on deviations of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1, especially related to person-months per work package.

Include explanations on transfer of costs categories (if applicable).

Include explanations on adjustments to previous financial statements (if applicable).

In order to implement the 3rd cycle, all the WPs continued active until the end of the project, even if when their estimated end in DoA had been set before, so more effort was invested by quite all the partners in terms of person/months in particular in WPs where networking, valorisation and facilitation of dialogues and research activities were managed. The increase in person / months does not change significantly the budget assigned to staff costs and its distribution among the partners, considering that the hourly cost of the personnel contracted was in many occasions lower than the hourly cost considered in the budget.

Below are the details of the reviews requested by the EU from each partner

USAL

EC requested revision: Regarding travel costs claimed for the visit in Las Vegas to attend the Human-Computer Interaction International Conference, 15-20.07.2018, could you please provide information as to which tasks specifically the travel costs refer to? What was the purpose of this visit and its contribution to the project?

Only the registration fees of the two participants were supported by the WYRED budget. Travel costs were paid from the research team's own funds.

WYRED project was presented in one of the most significant international conferences in Human-Computer Interaction area, the 20th HCI International Conference, which was held in Las Vegas, NV, USA on July 15-20, 2018.

First, one of the usability tests of the WYRED platform was presented and a paper was published in this book that is indexed in Google Scholar, Scopus and Web of Science:

F. J. García-Peñalvo, A. García-Holgado, A. Vázquez-Ingelmo y A. M. Seoane-Pardo, "Usability test of WYRED Platform," en Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Development and Technological Innovation. 5th International Conference, LCT 2018, Held as Part of HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part I, P. Zaphiris y A. Ioannou, Eds. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, no. 10924, pp. 73-84, Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2018. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-91743-6_5.

This paper has 110 cites in Google Scholar, and 6 cites in Scopus.

The paper was invited to be extended and was published in the journal Universal Access in the Information Society in 2019. The published paper is:

F. J. García-Peñalvo, A. Vázquez-Ingelmo, A. García-Holgado y A. M. Seoane-Pardo, "Analyzing the usability of the WYRED Platform with undergraduate students to improve its features," Universal Access in the Information Society, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 455-468, 2019. doi: 10.1007/s10209-019-00672-z.

The journal indicators are:

JCR SCIE – COMPUTER SCIENCE, CYBERNETICS – Q4 (18 de 23) – IF 0.920; JCR SSCI – ERGONOMICS – Q4 (15 de 16) – IF 0.920); (SJR 0.348 – COMPUTER NETWORKS AND COMMUNICATIONS – Q2; HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION – Q2; INFORMATION SYSTEMS – Q2; SOFTWARE – Q2); (CiteScore 1.99; COMPUTER NETWORKS AND COMMUNICATIONS – Q2

This paper has 3 cites in Scopus, 1 cite in WoS, and 46 cites in Google Scholar.

Besides, a video about the WYRED platform was selected in a video competition of the conference. This video was played in the biggest coffee break room for more than 2,500 persons during all days of the conference. This is the reference of the video:

A. García-Holgado y F. J. García-Peñalvo, "WYRED Platform, the ecosystem for the young people," presentado en HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, 2018. Disponible: <https://youtu.be/TRDjN5boky8>. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.1322032.

This video has 73 cites in Google Scholar.

EC requested revision: The average person month costs claimed by USAL in the second cost claim (3 096,53 EUR) correspond almost exactly to the average salaries reported in Period 1 (3 157,34 EUR). Please be reminded that beneficiaries may claim only actual costs (see Article 6 – Eligible and ineligible costs of the MGA). Please confirm that you have complied with this rule. The amounts of total declared costs and funding are close to the total estimated costs and funding foreseen in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

The personnel costs stated for the RP2 comply with both art. 6 (Grant Agreement), according to which personnel costs must be eligible and with Spanish national law to conclude a contract. On the one hand, the costs are eligible, since to calculate them, we have only had into account the concepts of salary, social security contributions and a final compensation at the conclusion of the contract. On the other hand, the kind of contract concluded agrees with that of a researcher. In the same line, the social security paid by the employer, the University of Salamanca, complies with our labour regulations that ask the employer to pay researchers according to their academic achievements (Group 1: workers in possession of a bachelor's degree). It doesn't matter that the average costs have hardly varied in relation to RP1, since the cost of living hasn't varied significantly either.

OXFAM

EC requested revision: There appears to have been approximately 32% increase in the person month costs (RP2 – average salary: EUR 2 799,57, personnel costs claimed in the Financial Statement: EUR 27 771,70 for 9.92 PM), in comparison to the average salaries from Period

1 (EUR 2 122,97). Please verify whether a mistake was made in the number of person months / costs reported. Otherwise, please justify the increase in the average personnel costs.

We do confirm the number of person months/costs reported.

The increase from Period 1 and Period 2 is due to two different factors:

- Salary increase considering the project started in November 2016 and ended in October 2019. During this period there were some salary adjustments due to internal policies and evolutions in the national legislation. Moreover, also the nature of the contracts changed. In fact, almost all staff with contracts equivalent to employment ones, were transformed in actual employment contracts as per new requirements set by national legislation limiting the use of equivalent contracts.
- To fulfill project activities planned during the Period 2 it was deemed necessary making recourse to persons with more professional experience and consequently with an higher hourly cost

EC requested revision: Please also verify whether the personnel costs charged fulfil the conditions set out in Article 6 - Eligible and ineligible costs of the MGA. The amounts of total costs and funding correspond exactly to the total costs and funding budgeted in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

Personnel costs charged to the project fulfil the conditions set out in Article 6. In particular, personnel costs claimed are actual costs.

PYE

EC requested revision: The amounts of total declared costs and funding are very close to the total estimated costs and funding foreseen in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

The calculation of the staff costs is based on the actual staff costs incurred for the implementation of the tasks for the project. This is backed up by the time records and pay slips in the case of employees with no project-based remuneration and contracts and payments in the case of natural persons working under a direct contract.

DOGA

EC requested revision: The Partner 4. DOGA is claiming some costs for purchasing “URkund Licenced program to detect and prevent the plagiarism in research projects”. Can you please clarify how these costs are linked to the project? Please remove from the cost claim costs that are not eligible (see Art. 6 of the MGA).

The actual cost of the URkund Licenced software has been removed, which decreased the overall sum of the other direct costs.

The amounts of total declared costs and funding are close to the total estimated costs and funding foreseen in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

The staff costs have been calculated on the basis of the actual staff costs incurred to implement the tasks.

YEU

EC requested revision: There appears to have been approximately 63% increase in the person month costs (RP2 – average salary: EUR 4 673,94, personnel costs claimed in the Financial Statement: EUR 29 773 for 6,37 PM), in comparison to the average salaries from Period 1 (EUR 2 865,39). Please verify whether a mistake was made in the number of person months / costs reported. Otherwise, please justify the increase in the average personnel costs. Please also verify whether the personnel costs charged fulfil the conditions set out in Article 6 - Eligible and ineligible costs of the MGA. The amounts of total personnel costs, total costs and funding correspond almost exactly to the total estimated personnel costs; total costs and funding budgeted in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

The change in YEU average salary came with the change of staff category involved in the project and the average daily rate of the personnel involved increased accordingly.

The previous staff members of YEU involved had lower average salary (19 EUR hourly rate) due to the position held (Project and Policy Officer) while in the second period, the person involved had an hourly rate of 30,75 EUR (position of Secretary General).

The change of staff category happened due to the importance of the project for the organisation and importance of quality contribution to the finalisation of all the required deliverables of the project.

MOVES

EC requested revision: It appears that no equipment costs have been foreseen in Annex 1 (see the section 3.4 Resources to be committed of Part B, p. 34). As the beneficiary MOVES claims in its financial statement some equipment costs (see: “Facilitators Toolcase” and “Computer for Facilitation”), please justify briefly in the REPORT ON EXPLANATIONS ON THE USE OF RESOURCES, how these costs relate to the project. For costs not foreseen in Annex I, please change 'YES' to 'NO' under the tab 'Foreseen in Annex I' and add the required explanation. Could you please clarify what is meant by “Costs for the Association”? Please verify if these costs are eligible under the category Other direct costs (as per Article 6 of the MGA). Please update the financial statement, if necessary. The travel cost (EUR 582.16) to the meeting in Luxembourg declared in the financial statement is an estimated amount. Please verify if this is the final amount. Please update the financial statement, if necessary. For the trips to the project meetings in Brussels, Belfast, Bath and Luxembourg, please add the dates when the trips took place. The beneficiary claims in the financial statement the costs of “gifts for EYE Participants”. Please note that in H2020 entertainment or hospitality expenses are not eligible (see Art. 6, p. 39 of AGA). Please remove ineligible cost from the financial statement.

- The “Computer for Facilitation” was removed, as it was used only at the very end of the WYRED project after the old computer used in the dialogues (WP5) and the research phases /WP6) stopped working.
- The “Facilitators Toolcase” was needed and used for moderation in WP5 – Dialogues and WP 6 Reseach activities. YES was Changed to NO on the portal.

- “Costs for the Association”: The Wyred Association was founded in Austria by the partners MOVES and Boundaries, Costs related to this are:
 - 1) Kompany (Austrian registry of companies) Excerpt of legal status MOVES: 17,69 €
 - 2) Certified translation of the Legal status of Boundaries into German (Evelyn Brandstetter Übersetzungsbüro): 78 €
 - 3) Association registration fee for the "Landespolizeidirektion Wien": 22,1 €. YES was Changed to NO on the portal.
 - The estimated costs for the review meeting in Luxembourg were changed to final costs of 571,16€.
 - The “gifts for EYE Participants” were removed.

The average person month costs claimed by MOVES in the second cost claim (EUR 4 974,58) correspond almost exactly to the average salaries reported in Period 1 (EUR 4 882,49) and budgeted in Annex 1 (EUR 4 875,46). Please be reminded that beneficiaries may claim only actual costs (see Article 6 – Eligible and ineligible costs of the MGA). Please confirm that you have complied with this rule.

MOVES as SME declared the personnel costs based on the amount per unit set out in Annex 2a (unit costs).

According to the article 6 of the AMGA, we understand that the request “***Please be reminded that beneficiaries may claim only actual costs***” is not applicable in the case of unit costs.

In article 6 of the AMGA, it is said: "The beneficiaries must be able to show the link between the number of units declared and the work on the action. The beneficiaries must be able to show (with records and supporting evidence; see Article 18) that the number of units declared was actually used for the action. (The actual costs of the work are not relevant.)

Example: A beneficiary which is an SME declares for its owner who does not receive a salary 300 hours worked for action in 2014. If there is an audit, the SME beneficiary must be able to show a record of the number of hours worked by the owner for the action. "

BOUNDARIES

EC requested revision: The beneficiary BOUNDARIES claims in the financial statement the same amount of subcontracting costs of EUR 10 000 for video production as it has been planned in Annex 1. Please add more information in the REPORT ON EXPLANATIONS ON THE USE OF RESOURCES under ‘Description’, by breaking the subcontracting costs down into the costs of individual subcontractors, WP and the name of the action task they are linked to. Please also note that in H2020 only action tasks to be performed should be subcontracted. The subcontracting does not include a purchase of a service, for example like a contract for the creation of a website that enables action's beneficiaries to work together (creating the website is not an action task). See also Article 13 and Article 10 of the Annotated Grant Agreement. The price for the contract can be then declared as 'other direct costs' in the financial statement. Please verify if the production of the video constitutes an action task.

Video production. This work is part of WP4 and relates to action task 4.3 (see page 70 of the proposal). One subcontractor was used for this work.

Task 4.3: Video. The creation of the video will be done by the lead valorisation partner with the support of the research partner BOUNDARIES, together with the youth partners, though

initial ideas will be brainstormed at the same time as the creation of the manifesto at the first project meeting. The actual video production will be subcontracted.

For the beneficiary 8. BOUNDARIES, there seems to be a discrepancy between the number of the total person months claimed in the Report on explanations on the use of resources (RP1: 8,59 PM + RP2: 16,93 PM = 25.52 PM) and the actual person months (21,54 PM) declared in the Technical Report (see the PM tables, p. 45 and 49). Please check the numbers especially for WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. Please clarify and correct the data where necessary.

The number of person months has been corrected in the financial statement.

The amounts of total declared costs and funding are close to the total estimated costs and funding foreseen in Annex 1. Please clarify if the costs claimed in your financial statements are actual.

BOUNDARIES as SME declared the personnel costs based on the amount per unit set out in Annex 2a (unit costs).

According to the article 6 of the AMGA, we understand that the request “***Please be reminded that beneficiaries may claim only actual costs***” is not applicable in the case of unit costs.

In article 6 of the AMGA, it is said: "The beneficiaries must be able to show the link between the number of units declared and the work on the action. The beneficiaries must be able to show (with records and supporting evidence; see Article 18) that the number of units declared was actually used for the action. (The actual costs of the work are not relevant.)

Example: A beneficiary which is an SME declares for its owner who does not receive a salary 300 hours worked for action in 2014. If there is an audit, the SME beneficiary must be able to show a record of the number of hours worked by the owner for the action. "

5.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable) [\(not applicable for MSCA\)](#)

Specify in this section:

- a) the work (the tasks) performed by a subcontractor which may cover only a limited part of the project;*
- b) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for a subcontract, taking into account the specific characteristics of the project;*
- c) the confirmation that the subcontractor has been selected ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price and avoiding any conflict of interests.*

No unforeseen subcontracting.

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in-kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges (if applicable) [\(not applicable for MSCA\)](#)

Specify in this section:

- d) the identity of the third party;*
- e) the resources made available by the third party respectively against payment or free of charges*

f) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for using these resources for carrying out the work.

No unforeseen use of in-kind contribution from third party.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	15.07.2015	Initial version
1.1	08.08.2016	Corrections for MSCA.
1.2	27.03.2017	Modification of Part B for Research Infrastructures (RI) actions to include a table with the resources used to provide access to RI.
2.1 (version of full template)	19.12.2017	Update of part B of the template to include explanations on adjustments to financial statements declared on previous periods.

6. References

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